

*Technoecology:
Machine Learning in
Bioacoustics &
Ecological Art*

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Table of Contents

Chapter 1 – Introduction	1
1.1 Motivation	1
1.2 Abstract	1
1.3 Research Outline	2
1.4 List of Publications	5
1.4.1 Primary Papers	5
1.4.2 Supporting Papers	7
Chapter 2 – Background	8
2.1 Ecological Monitoring: Motivations and Methods	8
2.2 ML and its Applications in Ecology	9
2.3 Passive Acoustic Monitoring of Ecosystems	11
2.4 Ecological Art and Artificial Environments.....	15
Chapter 3 – Research Results.....	18
3.1 Summary of Research Results and Contributions	18
3.1.2 Datasets and Source Code	24
Chapter 4 – Discussion of Research Results	26
4.1 Topic 1: ML & acoustics extend ecology	26
4.2 Topic 2: Technology alters our relationship to nature	30
Chapter 5 – Conclusions and Future Work	36
5.1 – Conclusions	36
5.2 Topic 1: Considerations and Future Work	37
5.3 Topic 2: Considerations and Future Work	38
References	40
Papers.....	50

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Chapter 1 – Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The stresses facing ecosystems in the Anthropocene are many and well-documented. Ecological monitoring has long aided in establishing anthropogenic impacts—such as those from land use change [1], [2], [3], [4] and climate change [5], [6], [7], [8]—and has served as a quantitative basis for sociopolitical action and conservation policy [9], [10], [11]. However, the complexity and intensity of environmental pressures is accelerating, in turn necessitating more complete ecological monitoring. Recent advancements in machine learning [12], [13] and low-cost sensors [14] have enabled ecologists to expand the scale and resolution of ecological monitoring [15], [16], [17]. Notably, the field of bioacoustics has experienced rapid growth, with automated vocalization detections [12] and soundscape-scale analyses [18], [19] supporting large-scale acoustic monitoring efforts. This increasing flow of natural information forms a hybrid “technoecology” [20], where nature is increasingly digitalized in order for us to make sense of our effects on it. This thesis aims to explore how technology broadly, and machine learning specifically, can progress ecological monitoring, while also considering how it affects our perception of nature and our relation to it.

1.2 Abstract

Ecosystems face a myriad of anthropogenic pressures, from global warming to habitat loss, which threaten a collapse of biodiversity and of the ecosystem services on which we depend. Recent advancements in machine learning (ML) and automation have enabled ecologists to expand the scale of ecosystem monitoring, capturing both large-scale spatial trends and fine-scale temporal trends impossible with manual surveys. The field of bioacoustics has increasingly gained attention in this context, as automated vocalization detection has enabled real-time passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) of biodiversity and animal phenology. This increased digitization of nature promises to enhance our environmental stewardship, but also shifts our perception of nature and our relation to it.

This thesis consists of two topics. First, we explore the applications of automation and large-scale data analysis to the study of avian phenology and biodiversity with a focus on bioacoustic methods. In this topic, we demonstrate that ML can extract insights on avian phenology from trans-continental scale ecoclimatic data. We next apply PAM in a national park setting, demonstrating at a fine temporal scale that engine noise affects avian vocalization phenology. We then expand our PAM scope with one of the first national-scale acoustic studies of avian biodiversity and migration phenology, using acoustic recorders installed across the latitudinal extent of Norway. We demonstrate that an autonomous PAM system can capture spring migratory arrival dynamics, fill data gaps in traditional manual surveys, and be

leveraged to generate continuous maps of avian vocalization that can support the timing and planning of traditional breeding bird surveys.

In the second topic, we delve into how technology affects our relationship to nature and our perception of it. We first build a novel ML model trained on global environmental soundscapes capable of generate novel pseudo-natural sounds, showing that increased environmental monitoring has already provided the raw data necessary for ML models to generate artificial nature. We discuss how such artificial nature can be artistically interesting in certain contexts but is far from a complete replacement for true natural. We next discuss how immersion in nature improves personal and societal well-being, as well as the aesthetics and ethics of artificial environments in this context. We demonstrate a case-study of ecological sound art using the recordings collected across Norwegian forests that leverages technology to expand the human senses. One is thus able to develop an aesthetic relationship to large-scale natural phenomenon, such as the spring migration of birds over thousands of kilometers.

1.3 Research Outline

This section outlines the structure of the thesis (Figure 1) and establishes the research questions that will be addressed. The thesis seeks to apply advancements in data science and ML to improve the capabilities of ecological monitoring and modeling (Topic 1) while simultaneously accounting for how increased digitalization of nature affects our perception of it (Topic 2). We explore these topics primarily through the lens of bioacoustics.

Figure 1. Research overview of the thesis. The primary research goal is organized into two topics, respectively focusing on its quantitative and qualitative aspects. Each topic is broken down further into a set of research questions, which are supported by one or more papers.

Topic 1: ML & acoustics extend ecology

Research Question 1: *Can ML models extract ecoclimatic insights from intercontinental data?*

Many bird species in North and South America migrate northwards in the Spring for the breeding season and Southwards in the Fall to escape winter conditions. These migration phenologies evolved to adapt to ecoclimatic cues which are now shifting under climate change [21], [22], [23], impacting the flowering cycles of plants [7], and the timing of food availability [24]. Understanding how changes in these cues impact phenology is critical information for conservation efforts. With large amounts of ecoclimatic and bird observation data available, ML offers one approach for finding ecological trends.

The following research sub-questions are addressed:

- 1.1. *Can an ML algorithm predict citizen science checklists of migratory birds based upon climatic variables?*
- 1.2. *Does lagged climate data serve as a better predictor of migratory bird occurrence than the current climate?*
- 1.3. *Can an ML model identify simple spatial relationships when relating climate to bird observation data?*
- 1.4. *What can an ML model tell us about how bird migratory phenology may change with the warming climate?*

Research Question 2: *Does PAM reveal engine noise effects on bird vocalizations?*

Noise pollution is an invisible pressure on ecosystems that disrupts animal communication [25], causes stress [26] and increased vigilance [27], and has downstream effects on fitness and biodiversity [2], [28]. Several studies have documented the long-term deleterious effects of anthropogenic noise *in situ* [1], [2], [25]. Less attention has been paid to short term behavioral effects of noise, and to effects during the winter season. Snowmobile noise has become a contentious issue in some areas such as U.S. National Parks [29], [30] and passive acoustic monitoring offers one method of evaluating bird behavioral responses to such engine noise.

The following research sub-questions are addressed:

- 2.1. *Can snowmobile noise be accurately detected in passive acoustic monitoring data with ML?*
- 2.2. *Does snowmobile noise affect the short-term vocalization phenology of birds?*

Research Question 3: *Can PAM support avian biodiversity and phenology monitoring at national scales?*

Avian migration and biodiversity dynamics play out on huge spatiotemporal scales, making ecological monitoring challenging for traditional survey approaches. While popular, open citizen science data such as eBird lack consistent spatiotemporal sampling [31] and must contend with observer error and bias [32]. Breeding bird surveys, on the other hand, are performed by trained volunteers, but are temporally limited to the breeding season and have only one annual observation made per survey point [10], [11], limiting applicability in temporal studies. Passive acoustic monitoring is growing in popularity due to advances in automation and low-cost sensors and its ability to provide real-time and high-resolution ecological data [15]. In this study we installed 28 networked acoustic sensors in forests across the latitudinal extent of Norway to track migration phenology and biodiversity.

The following research sub-questions are addressed:

- 3.1. *Is the popular BirdNET algorithm effective for automatically labeling bird vocalizations?*
- 3.2. *How does a national-scale acoustic monitoring system compare to and supplement citizen science and open science bird observations?*
- 3.3. *Can acoustic recorders identify Spring arrival phenologies of migrating passerine birds?*

Topic 2: Technology alters our relationship to nature

Research Question 4: *Can ML generate effective pseudo-natural soundscapes for future generations?*

As natural soundscapes diminish in complexity with corresponding losses in biodiversity [33], we lose some of our ability to immerse ourselves in nature [34] and experience its mental [35], [36], physical [37], and eudaimonic [38] benefits. As these trends continue, forms of pseudo-nature may come to partially fill in the gaps. Increasing amounts of environmental data are collected each year [39], providing training data for ML models to generate infinite pseudo-natural media. In exploring this question, we train a custom PyTorch model to generate pseudo-natural soundscapes using thousands of hours of global nature recordings.

The following research sub-questions are addressed:

- 4.1. *Can a deep learning model generate infinite pseudo-natural soundscapes for future generations?*
- 4.2. *What are the aesthetics and ethical implications of machine-generated nature in the context of real-world biodiversity collapse?*

Research Question 5: *What is effective ecological art and how can it improve nature affiliation?*

Research has demonstrated that immersion in nature supports mental and physical wellness [35], [37], in addition to eudaimonic pleasures such as self-actualization and personal relation to a culture or place [38], [40]. Audio [34], video [41], and virtual reality [41], [42] of nature can provide some of these same beneficial effects. Still, increased development and digitization of life has (naturally) resulted in less nature immersion [43]. In this way, we are increasingly depriving ourselves of the benefits of nature immersion and threatening the depth of our relation to nature. At the same time, digitization helps us to improve the monitoring and managing of ecosystems by extending our limited human senses [15]. This dichotomous situation highlights the usefulness of artistic methods, specifically digital art, for exploring our modern relationship to nature.

The following research sub-questions are addressed:

- 5.1. *How does nature immersion affect human individual and societal wellbeing and our connection to the natural world?*
- 5.2. *How can we leverage ecological data and computing to generate effective ecological art?*

1.4 List of Publications

This thesis is composed of five primary papers with my first or shared first authorship. Included for posterity are three relevant supporting papers where I am listed as a supporting author.

1.4.1 Primary Papers

Paper 1

Exploring the Spatiotemporal Influence of Climate on American Avian Migration with Random Forests [44]

A. Bick, V. Bakkestuen, M. Pedersen, K. Raja, S. Sethi
Under Review

Contribution: Led experimental design, data analysis, and writing of the manuscript.

Paper 2

Snowmobile noise alters bird vocalization patterns during winter and pre-breeding season [45]

B. Cretois*, **A. Bick***, C. Balantic, F. B. Gelderblom, D. Pávon-Jordán, J. Wiel, S. S. Sethi, D. H. Betchkal, B. Banet, C. M. Rosten, T. A. Reinen

Journal of Applied Ecology. 2023; <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14564>

*Benjamin Cretois and Ian Avery Bick contributed equally to this work.

Contribution: Devised and implemented bucketing methodology to analyze temporal relationships between engine noise and avian vocalization phenology. Drafted half of the manuscript, along with Benjamin Cretois.

Paper 3

National-scale acoustic monitoring of avian biodiversity and migration [46]

A. Bick, V. Bakkestuen, B. Cretois, B. Hillier, J. A. Kålås, M Pedersen, K. Raja, C. Rosten, M. Somveille, B. G. Stokke, J. Wiel, S. S. Sethi

Under Review

Contribution: Led acoustic recorder site selection process. Contributed to the installation and recovery of recorders in the field. Performed all analyses and led writing of the manuscript.

Paper 4

Building a Nature Soundscape Generator for the Post-Biodiversity Future: A pilot machine learning model for generating infinite pseudo-natural soundscapes [47]

A. Bick

Proceedings of the Conference on AI and Musical Creativity. 2023;

<https://aimc2023.pubpub.org/pub/soundscapes>

Contribution: Aggregated global soundscape datasets. Designed, built, and trained PyTorch model to generate soundscapes. Wrote the manuscript.

Paper 5

Simulated Environments and Environmental Consciousness: Extending Ecoacoustic Monitoring into Sound Art [48]

A. Bick

Under Review

Contribution: Performed relevant research and data mining, created the sound art case study of the Sound of Norway project, and wrote the manuscript.

1.4.2 Supporting Papers

Paper 6

Limits to the accurate and generalizable use of soundscapes to monitor biodiversity

S. S. Sethi, **A. Bick**, R. M. Ewers, H. Klinck, V. Ramesh, M. N. Tuanmu & D. A. Coomes *Nature Ecology & Evolution*. 2023; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02148-z>

Contribution: Used high performance computing to compute machine-learned features and other soundscape indices for large acoustic datasets. Commented on and approved manuscript.

Paper 7

Large-scale avian vocalization detection delivers reliable global biodiversity insights

S. S. Sethi, **A. Bick**, M. Y. Chen, R. Crouzeilles, B. V. Hillier, J. Lawson, C. Y. Lee, S. H. Liu, C. Henrique de Freitas Parruco, C. M. Rosten, M. Somveille, M. N. Tuanmu, C. Banks-Leite

The Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences. 2024;

Contribution: Led acoustic recorder site selection process for Norway dataset and contributed to the installation and recovery of recorders. Commented on and approved manuscript.

Paper 8

Forvaltningsrelevant bruk av akustikk for overvåking av norsk natur II: The Sound of Norway 2022

C. M. Rosten, **A. Bick**, B. Cretois, J. Fremstad, F. B. Gelderblom, D. Pavón-Jordán, T. A. Reinen, S. S. Sethi, J. Wiel.

Norwegian Institute for Research Technical Report 2215, 2023; <https://bibsys-almaprimo.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/permalink/f/ehvr8n/BRAGE11250/3043785>

Contribution: Led acoustic recorder site selection and contributed to recorder installation in the field. Generated Figures 2.2, 3.3, and 3.5. Commented on and approved manuscript.

Chapter 2 – Background

2.1 Ecological Monitoring: Motivations and Methods

Ecosystems are threatened globally by anthropogenic pressures. The loss and degradation of animal habitats, driven by climate change, agricultural and urban development, and pollution, threatens biodiversity [3], [4]. Additionally, rapid anthropogenic global warming induces instabilities in animal behaviors that have evolved over millennia of relatively stable ecoclimatic conditions [49], such as the annual spring and fall migrations of billions of birds [50]. Putting aside the compelling argument that nature should be protected for its own sake, earth's biodiversity provides countless invaluable services that make human society possible: clean water [4], food [4], limitation of climate change and its impacts [4], [51], as well as human mental and physical wellbeing [34], [35], [36], [38] and our sense of identity [36].

Ecological monitoring has demonstrated the effects of these pressures, providing a quantitative basis for conservation policies [11] as well as an increase in public awareness [9] that has been the impetus for political action [52], [53]. It has supported the planning and evaluation of conservation areas [54], the banning of chemical pollutants, and is commonly applied to evaluate the environmental impacts of development projects [9], [53], [55], [56]. Large-scale ecological monitoring was first made possible through early citizen science initiatives such as the North American Breeding Bird Survey [10] which has continued annually since in the 1960s, in which trained volunteers survey across pre-defined transects each spring, typically making a single observation at each site along a given transect. The resulting data have established long-term trends in bird populations [10], informed listings under the U.S. Endangered Species Act [11], evaluated drivers of bird population loss [57], and the effectiveness of conservation areas in protecting biodiversity [57].

Starting in the early 2000s, open citizen science apps such as eBird have allowed broader public participation in ecological monitoring [58]. Species observations in eBird take the form of checklists, in which participants note all species they observed, the effort of the survey (time spent and distance traveled), as well as the GPS location of the survey start point. If a participant notes that they have documented all species they observed, the survey is considered "complete" and pseudo-absences can be inferred for species not observed; complete checklists have been shown to improve the performance of species occurrence and detectability models [32]. Though open science datasets by their nature must contend with observer error and spatiotemporal biases [31], [32], these datasets have supported impressive modeling efforts of bird populations, ranges, and migration [59] and have supported federal conservation efforts in the U.S. such as the listing of threatened species [60] and collision risk modeling for wind energy development [61]. While incredibly useful for modeling of populations and trends over large spatiotemporal

scales, observations may be of insufficient resolution for avian monitoring in smaller regions or on finer timescales [62]. Additionally, concerns over data quality [21] and inconsistent spatiotemporal coverage [31], [63] may limit the application of data collected by non-specialists in some management applications.

Traditional surveys and citizen science datasets provide invaluable ecological monitoring data that has supported conservation efforts. At the same time, the ecological questions that can be answered using these methods are limited by their oftentimes sparse temporal resolution or uneven coverage [31], as well as by the manual effort they require. For example, questions regarding species' behavioral responses to human disturbances (such as engine noise [29]), the vocalization phenologies of species, the biodiversity in a specific area and times, and biodiversity in remote areas, are difficult to answer with openly available survey data. As the scale and complexity of ecological pressures has continued to increase [3], [4], it is critical that ecological monitoring likewise increases in both scale and resolution to document the effects of these stressors and to complement existing survey methods.

2.2 ML and its Applications in Ecology

Advancements in computing, automation, and data storage have fostered a recent evolution in ecological methods. Supported by expert validation [64], ML algorithms can act as force multipliers for ecologists and biologists by automating species detection through sound [13] and imagery [65], [66], reducing manual labor required for field work or manual classification, and reducing human error or spatiotemporal bias associated with open citizen science datasets. Broadly, ML involves training an algorithm to optimally perform a task, with the ability to adjust its own parameters to reduce error without explicit human intervention [67]. ML models are statistical tools that may be trained on masses of ecological data—such as soundscapes, survey observations, or camera trap images—to serve as predictive models and detect high-dimensional patterns. Deep learning (DL) models are a subset of ML models, typically based on neural network architectures, that often have many more trainable parameters than ML models, thus taking much longer to train and optimize [67]. ML and DL algorithms are often classified as either unsupervised, supervised, or reinforcement learning algorithms. Unsupervised and supervised algorithms are discussed below. Reinforcement learning concerns decision-making tasks that are dependent on changing states, such as self-driving cars or video game bots, and is thus outside the scope of this thesis. These topics will be reviewed below, but for a more comprehensive introduction to ML with Python see Raschka (2022) [68], and for reviews of ML applications in ecology see Pichler & Hartig (2022) [67].

Unsupervised learning broadly involves finding patterns and outliers across a dataset as-is, without the need for labeled examples. These methods can be used to cluster similar examples in a dataset together, detect anomalies, and to reduce the dimensionality of datasets [67]. Most relevant for this thesis are dimension

reduction algorithms—such as principal component analysis, Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP), and autoencoders—which seek to create new, and fewer, features to describe a given dataset more efficiently [67]. Unsupervised algorithms can be used to reduce dimensionality of complex data such as audio files to two-dimensions, so that one may plot a dataset and view outliers, such as audio detections of gunshots or other human activity in a natural setting [19]. In the variational autoencoder developed for Paper 4 of this thesis, for example, five-second ecological soundscapes are compressed into a single array of 1,024 numbers, with the model trained to reproduce the original soundscapes based on this array.

Supervised learning broadly involves using labeled datasets to relate predictor variables to a desired output variable. It is typically split into either classification or regression tasks [67]. Classification algorithms predict discrete outputs, such as assigning a specific species name to a photo or audio recording. Their goal is to minimize the error between its predictions and user-provided labels so that the algorithm may perform well on labeling new, unseen data. Common use cases of ML classification in ecological settings include predicting the presence of a specific species images from camera trap images [66] or identifying a specific species vocalization from a recording [12]. In Paper 3, for example, we apply the state-of-the-art DL bird vocalization classification model BirdNET [12] to identify specific species based on audio recordings collected from our recorders in the field. BirdNET uses a deep convolutional model architecture based on ResNETs [69], originally developed for image recognition. The convolutional aspect refers to a model's ability to process grid-like data (such as images) and extract informative features such as edges or textures that help to classify (supervised learning) or compress (unsupervised learning) input images.

Indeed, many deep convolutional model architectures first developed for image recognition techniques are applied in bioacoustics [13]. As is the case with BirdNET, audio recordings may be converted into a spectrogram, an image representation of the magnitude of specific frequencies over time. BirdNET was trained on over 200,000 bioacoustic audio files from the open-source libraries, containing a mix of expert and amateur labels of any present bird species [12]. Due to the massive quantities of data required to train such DL models, the presence of some incorrect labels is likely, which may impact model performance [12]. Thus, for species identification in ecological contexts, the use of DL classification models may be paired with expert validation of a sample of their output predictions [46], enabling researchers to maximize efficiency while maintaining accuracy.

In contrast, supervised regression algorithms are applied when predicting a continuous numerical output, such as the probability of a specific species occurring in a region, also with the goal of minimizing error between user-provided observations and model predictions. A commonly used supervised regression algorithm in ecology is the random forest regressor [70], [71], [72], a form of decision tree model. In random forest regressors, many random subsets of the

dataset's predictor variables and output variables are first sampled. During model training, the model learns how to best split these subsets to minimize the prediction error, performing such splits until a specific depth or subset size is reached. For example, when predicting the probability of a bird species appearing on eBird checklists (as in Paper 1), the model may find that splitting training data into cases where maximum temperatures are over or under 15°C is the best way to gain more information on whether this species occurs on a checklist. The output probability that the random forest predicts is the average of the predictions of all trees, the logic being that as an ensemble, many weak learners create a strong learner. Additionally, the features that most effectively split the training data can be identified, providing a metric of feature importance for prediction and a degree of transparency in often black-box ML models.

The rise of ML in ecology is supported in part by the increasing availability of geospatial data including species detections, current and projected climate, and land cover [73]. By relating species occurrence to climate and land cover, statistical [74] and ML [75], [76] based species distribution models have enabled a wide array of research, such as evaluating the potential impacts of climate change [77], [78], animal movement [79], and the spread of invasive species [73]. Even with these capabilities, examples of direct integration of ecological monitoring and modeling into conservation policy are quite limited in published scientific papers [54], [80]. This highlights the need for scalable [81] and standardized [82], [83] ecological monitoring methods, as well as a more holistic approach for researchers, including coordination with stakeholders [80] and public-facing science communication [15], [80].

2.3 Passive Acoustic Monitoring of Ecosystems

Technological advancements—in particular automation, data storage capacity, edge and cloud computing, and low-cost sensors [13], [84]—have fostered a recent acceleration of acoustic techniques in ecological studies [13]. Until the mid- to late-2010s, the scale of acoustic methods had been limited largely to pilot-scale initiatives due to the manual labor necessary for collecting audio and labeling detections, as well as the cost of recorders [84]. However, long-term, large-scale, real-time PAM of ecosystems is becoming increasingly workable [15], [16], [17], though the field is still nascent [13]. PAM is a scalable and non-invasive method of examining ecological communities and change [15], [16] using semi-autonomous recorders *in situ*, often powered by solar panels [15], [16] (see Figure 2). Recording systems can leverage wireless communication networks to transmit data or detections in near-real-time [15] and use ML algorithms to provide reliable vocalization detections in both terrestrial [12] and aquatic [85] ecosystems. When supported by expert validation, these algorithms drastically reduce labor associated with detection labeling and manual surveys [17], [81].

Figure 2. A solar-powered passive acoustic monitoring station with battery and networked Bugg recorder installed during the Sound of Norway [17], [46] project in 2022. Photo by Author.

Soundscapes captured by PAM can also be converted into embeddings by pre-trained audio classification models, which effectively compresses audio information into a list of numbers that represent an audio sample's location in the model's latent space. These compressed representations have been demonstrated to be correlated with biodiversity within an ecosystem [18], [81], may correlate with the presence of non-vocalizing species [18], and can detect outlier events such as gunshots [19] or engine noise [45]. When used with dimensionality reduction tools like UMAP [86], embeddings can generate compelling representations of cyclical changes in natural soundscapes [19] (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. A 2-dimensional UMAP compression and representation of high dimensional VGGish soundscape embeddings calculated from a year of continuous soundscape recordings from a passive acoustic monitoring microphone at the Cornell Lab of Ornithology. The cyclical nature of the annual soundscape is visible, with winter months clustering on the left, spring months on the bottom and bottom right, and summer months in the center. Circles and numbers represent the centroid of each month's soundscape embeddings. Derived from unpublished analysis by Author.

PAM especially holds promise for the tracking of bird biodiversity and behavior compared to traditional point count surveys, due to bird species' tendency to vocalize. This promise accelerated by the open availability of effective detection algorithms such as BirdNET [12]. Due to its fine temporal resolution, PAM can reveal diurnal patterns in avian activity [87], detect the presence of rare species [88], and explore effects of noise on animal behavior [45]. For example, previous studies of noise effects on animals have documented its deleterious effects, but have been somewhat limited in spatiotemporal scope due to reliance on manual labor, utilizing manual point counts [1], relying on manual collection of specimens [2] and samples [89], or manual annotation of recorded audio [90].

PAM may also serve as a gap-filling complement to existing breeding bird surveys, which lack temporal resolution, and open citizen science datasets, which have inherent spatiotemporal bias in sampling and observer skill [31], [84]. Overall, PAM offers an expansion of the possible spatiotemporal scales of ecological research and monitoring (see Figure 4). It pushes scientific capabilities towards the fully automated monitoring of ecosystems, with the motivation of gaining a deeper

and conservation: measuring biodiversity while simultaneously detecting potential illegal activity in protected areas such as logging or gunshots [19]. The Australian Acoustic Observatory, another notable PAM project, has demonstrated a continental-scale acoustic monitoring system of 360 continuously monitoring stations, with all recordings available periodically for research purposes [16]. The lack of real-time capability allowed for a simpler implementation and a larger spatial scale by removing the need to pay for mobile or satellite data transfer, while maintaining scientific use cases, such as evaluating ecosystem responses to fire events [16] or the monitoring of endangered species [92].

In this thesis, we seek to explore the capabilities of PAM on a national scale through the Sound of Norway project. We install several dozen networked recorders across the latitudinal extent of Norway, seeking to map biodiversity and capture avian migration phenology using PAM [17]. Additionally, we compare PAM observations of migrating species with a traditional breeding bird survey and the open citizen science dataset eBird [58] to elucidate how PAM may fill temporal gaps in these datasets, inform the timing of surveys for maximum detectability of species, and contribute to large-scale avian biodiversity monitoring. This project in part led to the TABMON project [93], a transnational bioacoustics project currently underway which seeks to capture avian biodiversity metrics and migration phenology across the European continent.

2.4 Ecological Art and Artificial Environments

Technology is advancing us towards the real-time autonomous monitoring of ecosystems. Such comprehensive monitoring will support conservation efforts and research on ecological stressors by endowing ecologists with expanded senses and tools. However, it is clear that advances in technology and automation are not universally positive from a socioenvironmental point of view, from the power requirements for model training and computing to the potential of economic inequality exacerbation [94]. Advancements in automation and computing have also facilitated the explosion of digital media—such as social networks, video, virtual reality, and video games—which have contributed to feelings of dissociation and depersonalization [95], as well as a loss of connectedness to nature [96]. As nature exposure has numerous demonstrated positive effects on wellbeing, including stress reduction [35], improvement in attention [35], and establishment of identify [97] and purpose [38], this increasing dissociation is concerning.

In *Connectedness as a Core Conservation Concern*, Zylstra *et al.* argue that our physical and psychological separation from nature is of core concern for conservation and that widespread connected with nature can support conservation outcomes [98]. In their conceptual framework, committed connectedness with nature is broadly predicated upon information about nature and experience in nature together fostering a feeling of “interrelatedness between one’s self and the rest of nature.” [98] Similarly, Malcolm Budd argues in *The Aesthetic Appreciation of Nature* that “aesthetic appreciation is deeper the more it is penetrated by and the

product of [scientific] knowledge.” [99] Scientific understanding allows us to understand our place in nature, and our effects on it. However, scientific understanding alone is insufficient for enabling conservation action—a statement to which many climate scientists [100] and ecologists [80] can attest.

There is clearly a dichotomy between technology’s ability to improve our knowledge of nature and its tendency to dissociate us from nature. Ecological art and aesthetics have a role to play in exploring this tension. In 2015, the notorious art piece *Ice Watch* [101], consisting of twelve large ice chunks excavated from Greenland weighing around 80 tons, was installed in Paris near the COP21 international climate talks [102]. The public was free to interact with and relate to the ice by laying on it, taking pictures with it, and even hugging it, while the ice slowly melted [102]. On a much larger spatiotemporal scale, scientists use remote sensing and observe the analogous shrinking of the earth’s ice caps, yet it is difficult to emotionally relate to data, and global action seems hamstrung despite our scientific understanding. The idea here is that scientific analysis provides important context, but there is something visceral that art can reveal to us about our “relationship to non-humans” [102] that helps to develop our interrelatedness with nature.

A nature recording, photograph, or landscape painting can be seen as *beautiful* (subtle, delicate) or *picturesque* (vibrant, complex) [103], but the limited scale of these items and their literal framing invokes the feeling of an art object rather than an open environment. On the other hand, an immersive experience in nature, such as the view after hiking a mountaintop or seeing Earth from the International Space Station, may evoke awe, vastness, oneness: the *sublime* aesthetic [103]. Ecological art that grasps at the scale of the *sublime* aesthetic can start to reveal more of environmental ‘hyperobjects’, a term coined by Timothy Morton that defines objects or phenomenon that are “massively distributed in time and space” [104, p. 1], and of which we can typically perceive only a small portion. A typical example of a hyperobject is global warming; we can perceive it through heat and through its destabilizing effects on nature and society, but it is impossible for us to perceive its full body. Our sensorial limitations in turn limit our ability to relate to these concepts and integrate their implications [104]. Art helps us explore and integrate these elusive hyperobjects. The aforementioned *Ice Watch* [101] circumvents our sensory limitations by bringing the melting ice to us, demonstrating the global warming hyperobject in a miniaturized and accelerated form, and allowing us to relate to it in a physical and tactile way.

Sound art is another method of “attuning our senses to superhuman timescales” [105]. The piece *Longplayer* by Jem Finer exemplifies this capability—it consists of six simultaneously running tracks playing excerpts from the same musical piece on singing bowls at varying rates, starting on December 31, 1999 in London and finishing its cycle in 2999 [106]. At a 2020 live performance of the piece in Amsterdam, a listener could experience the hecticness of everyday city life playing out alongside the expansive timescale of this piece, a reminder that the long timescales of hyperobjects such as climate change are playing out alongside our

more short-term concerns [105]. Sound art can also facilitate our emotional relation to broad socioenvironmental concepts. Merlin Coleman's *Explorations of Extraction and Decay* [107] is a spatial sound art piece centering around a quarry and a landfill. Coleman combines field recordings of huge industrial excavation and trash disposal operations and interviews of government officials, neighbors, and ecologists discussing the socioenvironmental implications of these projects. The piece cleverly weaves human experiences to the "broader phenomenon" [107] of waste and extraction, inviting the listener's own emotional connection to these concepts. In turn, such emotional responses to environmental issues have been linked to pro-environmental policy support [108], [109].

In this thesis, we leverage the nationwide acoustic sensor network installed through the Sound of Norway [17], [46] initially to study avian biodiversity and migration, but also to generate sound art pieces that explore the ecological hyperobject of Norway's forest ecosystems. With these far-flung recorders, we expand the human auditory sense across large distances with the intention of establishing an aesthetic appreciation of this ecosystem's vastness and cyclicalness, as well as its intersection with other phenomenon such as biodiversity and avian migration. Unfortunately, the complexity of environmental soundscapes have been degrading due to long-term loss of biodiversity stemming from anthropogenic pressures [33]. As sound is a critical component in how we relate to our environment, this may affect both our ability to relate to nature, and the positive health effects of nature immersion. Digital forms of nature, such as virtual reality [41] or audio [34], have been shown to have some beneficial effects on mood or stress. To explore the potential of such pseudo-nature in a theoretical post-biodiversity future, we train a convolutional variational auto-encoder on 1700 hours of nature soundscapes from around the world to generate infinite pseudo-natural sounds through sampling and interpolation of its latent space. While rich in quantity, the overall result is a highly compressed artificial nature which borrows aesthetics from nature but lacks the context and physicality which mediate our relationship to nature [96], [97], [110]. While technology can enhance our understanding of nature, it cannot replace it one-for-one.

Chapter 3 – Research Results

3.1 Summary of Research Results and Contributions

Research Question 1: *Can ML models extract ecoclimatic insights from intercontinental data?*

Paper 1 introduced a novel modeling approach for exploring spatiotemporal relationships between climate data and avian biodiversity, as represented by eBird checklists. Our study ecoregion [111] in the Northeastern United States sees many passerine species migrating into the region for the spring breeding season, and Southward in the fall for winter. We trained an ensemble of simple ML models (random forest regression) on North and South American climate data to accurately predict the monthly occurrence of such migrating passerines on eBird checklists. Through an evaluation of feature important metrics, it is demonstrated that the models identify that North American climate features are more useful for prediction of species during October, a month where many species begin to migrate southward. Additionally, we find that climate data from July facilitated significantly lower error when predicting passerine species occurrences on eBird checklists three months later in October. This correlates with literature that suggests ecoclimatic conditions may have time-lagged effects on food availability and bird phenology and subsequently influence timing of breeding and migration [24], [112], [113]. While coarse in spatiotemporal resolution, this study shows that ML has the potential to extract relevant ecological insights from ecoclimatic data at huge scales. Future studies could utilize higher resolution data and incorporate vegetation indices as a proxy for the timing of greening and food availability for passerines. The ability to model how future changes in climate will affect the behavior of migrating birds, especially more vulnerable longer distance migrants [114], may aid in planning of land management for easing climate change adaptation in these species.

Addressing research sub-questions:

- 1.1. *Can a ML algorithm predict citizen science checklists of migratory birds based upon climatic variables?*

The random forest regressor models applied in this paper accurately predict the probability of eBird checklist occurrence (see Paper 1, Figures 2-3) based on minimum temperature, maximum temperature, and precipitation data. The mean absolute error of the monthly checklist occurrence across all 41 passerine species in our Northeastern United States study region ranged from 1.7 to 3.8 percent across the study period of 2009-2018. Error metrics were higher in spring and summer months when avian biodiversity and checklist occurrence probabilities were higher.

- 1.2. *Does lagged climate data serve as a better predictor of migratory bird occurrence than the current climate?*

For the prediction of eBird checklist occurrence in October, a month in which many passerine species are leaving or have left southward for the winter season, we found that climate data from 2-3 months earlier (the preceding July and August) led to significantly lower error in average mean absolute error across species, suggesting a lagged relationship between climate and avian phenology. This relationship was not found in April, a month where these passerine species are arriving in our study area from southern regions. This may be because the individuals that spend breeding season in our study region are spread out across broad regions in the winter season, so climatic effects on migratory behavior may be more distributed. Other studies have noted dependencies of both bird phenology [115] the availability of food sources, such as insects, to climate [24], but few or no previous studies have used an ML modeling approach to explore the short-term effects of climate on avian migratory phenology.

1.3. Can an ML model identify simple spatial relationships when relating climate to bird observation data?

Quantifying random forest feature importance in our model ensemble, we found that our ensemble identified North American climate features as significantly more important than South American climate features for predicting species presence in October in the Northeastern United States study region, but no relationship was found for species presence in April. This result suggests that ML models can correctly relate regional climate features to avian biodiversity. Future work with DL models may explore more localized effects of climate to avian phenology and biodiversity.

1.4. What can an ML model tell us about how bird migratory phenology may change with the warming climate?

Generally, literature has identified that mean bird migratory arrival in northern regions is advancing with global warming [115]. When applying a random forest regressor to predicting monthly occurrence of passerine species under 2021-2040 climate, we get mixed results. Projected species occurrence on eBird checklists increases in April but decreases on average in March. Decision trees, such as random forests, cannot predict outside the range of training data. Therefore, the effects of future increases in temperature are bounded within our model, potentially leading to conservative predictions. Future work may apply larger datasets and DL models without the constraints of decision trees to explore this research question.

Research Question 2: *Does PAM reveal engine noise effects on bird vocalizations?*

Paper 2 applies PAM, ML, and a temporal bucketing technique to demonstrate that bird vocalization frequency decreases immediately before the passing of snowmobiles, followed by a recovery in frequency of bird vocalization. It

demonstrates that a combination of ML detections and harmonic noise ratio filtering algorithmically identifies snowmobile noise with high recall (low false negatives), though precision (false positives) was more challenging, due to issues with wind noise. Overall, it is one of the first studies to establish the effects of snowmobile noise on bird behavior at a population-scale, filling a knowledge gap in winter season land management policy [29]. It opens the door for future studies on behavioral impacts of anthropogenic noise on birds *in-situ* at a population scale. Future studies could also distinguish between species and call types (alarm call, song, etc.) to develop a more complete understanding of impact for informed land management.

Addressing research sub-questions:

2.1. Can snowmobile noise be accurately detected in passive acoustic monitoring data with ML?

The snowmobile detector model developed by my co-author Benjamin Cretois, based on a pre-trained ResNext architecture [116], had high recall for detecting snowmobiles from PAM recordings, but low precision due to false positive detections on wind noise. An additional filter, the harmonic noise ratio, was required to improve the precision of detections. As engine noises are periodic in nature, and wind noise non-periodic, the use of harmonic noise ratio greatly improved precision. An additional filter, only including positive detections longer than 6 seconds in length, further improved precision and F1 score at the expense of recall. In short, a combination of DL methods and filtering was able to detect snowmobiles from PAM recordings with balanced precision and recall. A larger training set of snowmobile detections could support a solely DL approach to this task.

2.2. Does snowmobile noise affect the short-term vocalization phenology of birds?

Through bucketing of bird call detections in 15-second intervals preceding and following each snowmobile detection, we find that the log of vocalization frequency fits a negative linear model before snowmobile detections and a positive linear recovery afterwards. The effects were seen most strongly during mornings, as the dawn chorus is when bird vocalizations are typically most frequent. This demonstrates some of the first population-wide evidence of short-term effects of anthropogenic noise on bird vocalization phenology, particularly in the winter season.

Research Question 3: *Can PAM support avian biodiversity and phenology monitoring at national scales?*

Paper 3 exhibits one of the first near-real-time national-scale passive acoustic monitoring schemes. Across Norway, 28 recorders were installed to monitor avian biodiversity and migratory patterns, with many recorders transmitting data in near-real-time using cellular connections. The results show that PAM fills temporal data gaps in traditional survey data, enables mapping and tracking of avian biodiversity, and reveals fine-scale insight into migratory bird phenology. It also demonstrates that acoustic species distribution models (aSDMs) can be generated from vocalization data and used to estimate species detectability over space and time, and that these models agree with observations from eBird citizen scientists. Through this pilot study, we show that PAM, in tandem with automated species detection using ML, can support monitoring of biodiversity and phenology at a national scale. Future initiatives could consider permanent PAM installations for long-term data, incorporate a greater number of recorders, and use PAM networks to study effects of anthropogenic pressures along development gradients, as opposed to solely forest ecosystems as in this study.

Addressing research sub-questions:

3.1. Is the popular BirdNET algorithm effective for automatically labeling bird vocalizations?

We provided an expert ornithologist with the relevant audio for 50 BirdNET detections for 67 bird species, finding that the model predicted 57 species with over 80% precision, detecting 30 of these species at 100% precision (see Paper 3 Figure 1). However, several species had zero correct identifications by BirdNET. This highlights both the applicability for BirdNET for automation of bird vocalization identification and the need for expert validation of its predictions.

3.2. How does a national-scale acoustic monitoring system compare to and supplement citizen science and open science bird observations?

We find that PAM offer far higher temporal resolution and total observations than eBird and the Norwegian Breeding Bird Survey for detecting three common migrating passerine species, even when incorporating all detections from these two datasets within 90 x 90 km boxes around our recorders (see Paper 3 Figure 2). However, we also see that on days where both PAM and manual surveys were performed, the manual surveys were slightly more likely to detect these species, perhaps due to the use of only a handful of PAM recorders in each region. PAM detections were also used to train audio species distribution models, allowing us to map the probability of vocalization over the period of migratory arrival. Such maps could inform the timing of breeding bird surveys in different regions of Norway, so they occur during periods of high detectability. Overall, PAM provides temporal gap-

filling for manual survey data and monitoring of remote locations with little manual survey coverage.

3.3. *Can acoustic recorders identify Spring arrival phenologies of migrating passerine birds?*

Using PAM detections, we were able to generate cumulative audio detection curves for three common migrating passerines in several regions across Norway. We noted a general trend of steeper cumulative vocalization curves in the northern regions of Trondheim and Tromsø, where detections began soon after the first satellite detections of vegetation greenness. In these regions, the breeding season is shorter and birds arrive quickly as food and habitat becomes available after snow melts [117]. In contrast, we observe a more gradual cumulative vocalization curves in the more southernly areas of Bergen and Kristiansand, where vegetation is generally not covered by snow in the spring. We are also able to see a general trend of order of arrival, with Common Chiffchaffs arriving before Willow Warblers, followed by Spotted Flycatchers. This pattern corresponds to their respective diet, with Chiffchaffs and Warblers commonly foraging on crawling insects or seeds, while Flycatchers catch flying insects that emerge later in the spring season. Overall, the high temporal resolution of PAM allows for the generation of cumulative arrival curves at specific locations, enabling comparison of species arrival timing and relation of arrival to ecoclimatic variables.

Research Question 4: *Can ML generate effective pseudo-natural soundscapes for future generations?*

Paper 4 showcases a proof-of-concept DL model, trained on volumes of global nature recordings gathered from collaborators and open-source databases, that can generate infinite pseudo-natural soundscapes. It takes an ironic approach in demonstrating how future generations may experience nature soundscapes, assuming current degradation of natural soundscapes continues [33]. The prototype model has basic functionality, generating high-dimensional combinations of disparate global soundscapes, but without the context of their original ecologies (see [118, p. 146]). While future models will undoubtedly improve the quality and clarity of generated natural soundscapes, this paper serves to foretell that even if such procedurally-generated nature is believable, it will be unlikely to fully confer [41] the physical, mental, and social benefits of actual nature immersion [37], [40], [43], [43], [119].

Addressing research sub-questions:

4.1. *Can a DL model generate infinite pseudo-natural soundscapes for future generations?*

This pilot model shows that variational autoencoders can indeed generate pseudo-natural soundscapes by training on real soundscape data, compressing it into a high-dimensional vector, then sampling its latent space. Specific combinations of ecological soundscapes can be created by interpolating between two points in the test set within the model's latent space. Future models operating at higher resolutions may create infinite generative soundscapes by sampling continuously through such a latent space.

4.2. What are the aesthetics and ethical implications of machine-generated nature in the context of real-world biodiversity collapse?

As nature immersion has myriad physiological and psychological benefits, continued access to nature may be essential in the future if current trends of biodiversity collapse and global warming continue. Historical audio and visual recordings, in combination with generative DL, may serve as a superficial form of this immersion that lacks actual nature's materiality. Generative techniques, like the model piloted here, mine and combine aesthetics from their training data while draining its real world context (see [118]). This lack of context arguably limits our ability to emotionally relate to generative nature. In comparison, when listening to the biophony and geophony of a soundscape that we inhabit physically, we may also see animals communicating or physically feel the wind or rain, contributing to our immersion, our experience of the sublime aesthetic, and feelings of affiliation with nature. A main artistic motivation of Paper 4 is to elicit this comparison.

Research Question 5: *What is effective ecological art and how can it improve nature affiliation?*

Paper 5 provides a review of environmental aesthetics with a focus on how immersion in both real and digital nature can ameliorate mental and physical health. It discusses how advancements in PAM and media technology can be applied to create compelling ecological art that serves to expand our senses and affiliation with nature. It applies these principles in a sound art case study that compiles environmental recordings across the length of Norway, spatially panning sounds to match their approximate geographic locations, thereby allowing a listener to remotely experience huge spatiotemporal scales. The paper poses that such aesthetic experiences can develop our affiliation with environmental "hyperobjects" [104] that are impossible to fully experience with our own senses, such as ecosystems, or bird migrations. Our inability to experience these hyperobjects aesthetically may be challenging our ability to integrate ourselves in our changing ecology and climate (see [120]). Future ecological art may consider leveraging technology not to replace nature, but to deepen our aesthetic and emotional connection to larger spatiotemporal scales of ecology.

Addressing research sub-questions:

5.1. *How does nature immersion affect human individual and societal wellbeing and our connection to the natural world?*

On an individual level, studies have shown that nature immersion positively affects attention [35], [119], [121], stress levels [122], and life satisfaction [123]. Reduction of nature connectedness, partly due to prevalence of digital media [96], is a critical conservation concern, as this connectedness is correlated with pro-environmental beliefs behavior [98], [124]. Simulated environments such as nature soundscapes and virtual reality have been shown to have some of the psychological benefits of actual nature immersion [34], [41]. Further immersion in real nature, as well as the use of effective ecological art and media, are thus critical methods for building nature connectedness.

5.2. *How can we leverage ecological data and computing to generate effective ecological art?*

Malcolm Budd, a philosopher within environmental aesthetics, argues that our ability to experience only a “small time slice” of nature [99, p. 105], as well as our limited spatial perspective, limits our ability to aesthetically perceive an ecosystem. Our senses thus limit our ability to relate to environmental hyperobjects. Here, ecological art plays a role in immersing us within these hyperobjects in creative ways [101], or by using technology to indirectly expand our sensory range [125] or change our perspective [126]. In Paper 5 we leverage the PAM recordings of Sound of Norway project (see Paper 3) to curate sound art pieces that capture the spatial differences in forest soundscapes across the latitudinal extent of Norway. In this way we hope to use simulated environments as a “extension” [41] of nature that facilitates our aesthetic relationship to complex and distributed ecological concepts.

3.1.2 *Datasets and Source Code*

Availability of source code and data is critical for reproducibility of research and development of new models. The following Python code and datasets applied in this thesis are openly available:

- Paper 1:
 - Python notebooks, bird survey data, and geospatial data for training bird occurrence models and projecting future bird survey occurrence based on climate projections, as well as the code to generate all figures are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10157596>
- Paper 2
 - The audio snowmobile detection model developed by coauthor Benjamin Cretois is available at https://github.com/NINAnor/snowmobile_analyzer and bird detection results from BirdNET used in the bucketing analysis are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10259297>.

- Paper 3
 - Python notebooks, bird survey data, and geospatial data for comparison of passive acoustic monitoring to manual surveys, training of audio species distribution models, and generation of all figures are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11238951>
- Paper 4
 - Python notebook, audio spectrogram data, and pytorch model weight files for the pilot pseudo-natural soundscape generator are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13944293>

Chapter 4 – Discussion of Research Results

4.1 Topic 1: ML & acoustics extend ecology

Topic 1 of this thesis demonstrates that ML has a multifaceted capacity to further ecological research and monitoring. On one hand, ML improves modeling capability for ecological data, as in Paper 1 where simple ML models outperform linear models for the prediction of species occurrence. Indeed, the scientific literature shows that ML models outperform statistical or parametric models in many ecological contexts such as land cover classification from satellite imagery [127] and species distribution modeling [128]. ML algorithms excel at predictive modeling due to their ability to capture non-linear patterns and adapt model complexity flexibly to different datasets [67]. While often criticized as black boxes [129], analysis of ML model error and feature importance metrics can provide interpretability while also elucidating scientifically relevant patterns in underlying data. An analysis of these metrics in Paper 1 showcases that, when predicting bird species occurrence on eBird checklists during fall migratory departure in North America, the model correctly identifies spatially relevant climate features as more important for prediction. We also see hints of time-lagged effects of climate on biodiversity and bird migration phenology [24], [112], [113] during fall, with summer climate data being a better predictor of fall occurrence than the present conditions in fall. This case study, while using a simple model and coarse spatiotemporal resolution, suggests that ML may be a useful tool for modeling of bird species migration [79], especially as climate change continues to shifts their timing [22], [114].

As model complexity increases from linear models, to ML algorithms (such as random forest [70]) to many-layered DL algorithms (such as BirdNET [12]), model interpretability is further sacrificed towards higher prediction accuracy [129]. While challenging for some applications [129], [130], ML's general focus on predictive strength over interpretability lends itself neatly to the automation of ecological tasks. When a model performs well on a repetitive predictive task, such as identifying a species from a recorded vocalization [12] or a camera trap image [66], and its performance can be validated by a subject-matter expert (see Figure 4d and Paper 3), understanding the model's high-dimensional reasoning is less vital [46]. In this way, ML can extend the scope of ecological research and biodiversity monitoring by acting as a force-multiplier for ecologists. PAM is a prime example of this approach that leverages low-cost sensors and ML algorithms for broad spatial coverage, high temporal resolution, and automated and verifiable detections.

Paper 2 demonstrated how PAM enables novel ecological insights through a case study on snowmobile engine noise impacts on winter avian vocalization phenology in Yellowstone National Park in the United States (see Figure 5). Many previous studies have focused on detrimental effects of chronic noise on wildlife [2], [27], [90], [131]. Others have documented immediate behavioral effects of noise on wildlife but have relied on direct observation [30], [132], [133], [134], limiting study

scope. The U.S. National Park Service acknowledged such a data gap in their 2011 Yellowstone Final Winter Use Plan, "...it is difficult to conclude what effect, if any, over-snow vehicle use has on individuals or populations by observational studies alone." [29, p. 102]. In this paper, an analysis of PAM detections demonstrated that passing engine noise indeed affects avian behavior across the Park through reduced vocalization frequency as snowmobiles approach, which recovers after the snowmobiles pass. This reduction in the frequency of bird vocalizations is reminiscent of the effects of simulated predator risk, where frequency of song in passerine birds may be reduced immediately following the artificial playback of predator vocalizations [135]. Even though vocalization rates recover after a snowmobile pass, birds may experience increased vigilance and stress in noisy conditions, which may in turn decrease time spent foraging and reduce weight [2], [27], [136].

Figure 5. Histograms of the number of bird calls recorded A) before and B) after snowmobile engine noise detections in Yellowstone National Park during morning, afternoon, and evening. Lines and confidence bands show linear models fitted to the log of bird vocalization count with 95% confidence intervals. Displayed p-values represent the significance of pearson tests between the time of day and estimated marginal means of bird vocalizations. Excerpted from Paper 2 [45].

Overall, Paper 2 demonstrates that PAM can enable a more complete picture of ecosystem-wide phenomenon that fills in knowledge gaps for land managers and policymakers. One shortcoming of the study was the lack of distinguishing between bird species and call types: alarm calls, mobbing calls, or song. Future studies could leverage PAM to explore how call type frequency changes during the approach of engine noise, exploring on population-scales how many species react to anthropogenic noise. For example, responses could be compared in areas of high and low snowmobile traffic to test for noise habituation amongst birds. Additionally, while the custom ML model applied in Paper 2 for detection of snowmobile engine noise low false negatives (high recall), it struggled with false positives (low precision) due to wind noise. Noting the periodic nature of cycling engine noise relative to nonperiodic wind noise, we filtered all ML snowmobile detections for high harmonic noise ratios [137] as well as high model confidence. Taken together, these filtering methods increased precision from 0.11 to 0.50, with a recall of 0.98. These results highlight the need for rigorous validation of ML detections in PAM contexts, as well as the potential for further improvement of models for engine noise detection.

Due to the near-autonomous nature of recorders, PAM can be implemented across even larger scales than a national park. Paper 3 demonstrated one of the first implementations of PAM at a national scale, across the latitudinal extent of Norway. Like in Paper 2, the ML algorithm BirdNET was used for detection of bird vocalizations. However, here it was paired with expert ornithologist validation of the model's detections, allowing for study of specific species which the model has been shown to precisely identify—55 species, 14 of which were full-migrants, were detected with over 80% precision. With only 28 sensors nationwide, we were able to explore the migratory arrival timing of passerines in forests across Norway for several common species: Common Chiffchaff, Willow Warbler, and Spotted Flycatcher, finding that the timing of detections matched ecological intuition based on their respective diets of crawling insects and larvae (Common Chiffchaff, Willow Warbler) and later emerging flying insects (Spotted Flycatcher). We also demonstrated that when Willow Warbler arrived at higher latitudes, it tended to do so at a lower vegetation index, hinting at potential trade-offs between lower food availability and low intraspecies competition in these areas [117]. Indeed, in more northern areas with sharper greening curves (see Figure 3 in Paper 3), Willow Warbler seem to arrive more rapidly than in southern areas. At the onset of this rapid spring greening in the North, there may be a “climatic threshold” passed [117] where the costs of cold climate are outweighed by early access to optimal nesting sites and mates [117], [138]. Climate change shifts the annual timings of such ecological thresholds earlier, with some species (especially longer distance migrants) experiencing mismatches between optimal and actual arrival times [114]. A 2002 study of avian migration in Northern Norway showed some evidence of earlier migration in warmer years, though results were mixed and the study relied on volunteer birdwatcher observations, limiting sampling and inducing spatial bias towards populated areas [117]. A theoretical network of long-term PAM systems in remote Northern ecosystems could overcome limitations in existing data, providing

clear relationships between ecoclimatic conditions and the vocalization frequency of migrants.

We demonstrate the potential for PAM to both gap-fill existing survey methods and inform their optimal timing in Paper 3. Breeding bird surveys in the northern hemisphere are designed to capture a snapshot of bird population and biodiversity after all migratory species have arrived in the summer, with a general focus on monitoring long term populations of breeding pairs [10], [11]. These counts are valuable estimates of bird breeding success and population extents, but their limited temporal scope and the manual labor required limits their applicability to studies of bird phenology or migratory timing [139]. On the other hand, open citizen science datasets such as eBird [59] or artsobservasjoner [140] offer year-round bird detections and wide spatial coverage of bird detections by anyone in the public who wishes to contribute. These datasets can also be used to make large-scale models of species ranges over time, such as the eBirds status and trends dataset [141]. However, the underlying eBird survey data may require significant preprocessing to account for survey effort, distance traveled, surveyor experience, false detections, and spatiotemporal biases in sampling [32]—road density is a strong predictor for eBird survey density [31]. Indeed, a handful of PAM recorders may have far more complete temporal coverage and overall detections than both breeding bird surveys and eBird, even when including all manual surveys performed within a 90 x 90 km box surrounding the recorders. By training a simple random forest ML model on PAM species detections and relevant climatic variables, Paper 3 illustrated how PAM detections can also be utilized to create audio species distribution models (aSDMs) [77] that model a species' probability of vocalization spatiotemporally (see Figure 6). Such information could be useful in informing the timing of breeding bird surveys to occur at periods of high species detectability through their vocalizations and activity, especially as climate change shifts migratory bird arrival timing [114], [142]. Additionally, by using projected climate models, aSDMs can project how climate change may affect species vocalization patterns and habitat ranges [77].

Figure 6. Acoustic species distribution models (aSDMs) showing changes in vocalization probability of A) Willow Warbler and B) Spotted Flycatcher during migratory arrival in Spring 2022. The agreement of aSDM values with C) eBird checklists and D) Norwegian Breeding Bird Survey surveys, with p-values representing permutation test results, indicating whether aSDM values were significantly higher when each survey indicated a species was present versus when absent. Excerpted from Paper 3 [46].

4.2 Topic 2: Technology alters our relationship to nature

Topic 2 of this thesis explored the multifaceted importance of humanity’s relationship with nature and how it is affected and mediated by technology. It has been argued that we have an inherent “tendency to focus on life and lifelike processes” [143, p. 2], or a biophilia. This is intuitive, as we have recently (in evolutionary terms) shifted from the natural world to the man-made world, too quickly to “permit any major biological adaptations.” [144, p. 87]. It is also apparent that our environment affects our physical and mental state, and that technology has increasingly altered our environment throughout history. Unsurprisingly, studies have demonstrated that humans prefer the soundscapes [34] and imagery [145] derived from nature rather than in man-made areas like cities. Experience of nature has been associated with improved attention [35], [119], [121], [146], reduced stress [35], [147], and longevity [148], as well as broader eudaimonic feelings such as life satisfaction [149], personal growth [147], creative problem solving [43], and meaning [38]. In turn, such eudaimonic feelings have been correlated with biospheric values such as conservation [97]. Thus, it is crucial to foster and further

study the development of nature affiliation in the modern era to simultaneously support conservation and societal wellbeing [150].

Previous studies have explored if the positive effects of nature immersion and affiliation transfer to digital forms of nature. Indeed, listening to recordings of natural soundscapes have been associated with feelings of pleasantness [34] and with stress recovery [151]. A review of 21 studies regarding immersion in virtual reality (VR) nature found that it may decrease negative affect, such as fear or anxiety, though the literature is mixed [41]. Rather than a replacement of nature, such virtual nature may be viewed most accurately as “an extension of nature” [41], a possible supplement to our existing affiliation to nature that could include viewing aspects or scales of nature otherwise impossible to experience through bodily senses. Malcolm Budd argues in *The Aesthetic Appreciation of Nature* that our inability to observe the true spatiotemporal extent of an ecosystem—only a “small time-slice”—“presents a problem for the appreciation of the aesthetic value of that ecosystem” [99, p. 105]. Indeed, objects such as ecosystems are what Timothy Morton dubs “Hyperobjects”—objects or concepts that are “massively distributed in space and time relative to humans” and as such are difficult for our senses and minds to fully grasp [104, p. 1].

Paper 5 discussed how immersion in nature evokes the sublime aesthetic experience, how this relates to our affiliation with nature, and its physiological and psychological benefits. We discuss through examples how digital mediums extend natural aesthetics by exploring spatial and temporal scales otherwise impossible to reach with our senses. This includes a case study using original sound sculptures created using forest recordings collected with PAM data during the Sound of Norway project as part of this PhD. Each of these sound sculptures demonstrates the national soundscape in Norwegian forests in one month—May through July—capturing the peak of the arrival of long-distance migratory birds from Africa into Norway for the Spring and Summer, as well as the influence of midnight sun in northern areas on avian vocalization. In the acoustic space, we pan soundscapes and bird detections depending on their spatial location: the southernmost forests near Kristiansand towards the left, Trondelag region forests in the center, and the arctic soundscapes of Tromsø and Finnmark towards the right (see Figure 7). This sound art piece demonstrates that PAM data can be used in an artistic sense to expand human senses across these huge spatiotemporal scales, exploring how seasonal dynamics drive cyclical changes in ecosystems and animal behavior via their soundscapes. It can be argued that ecological art derived from monitoring data can reveal more of natural hyperobjects [104], allowing an aesthetic connection to be drawn to otherwise massive and fuzzy concepts such as “ecosystems” and “migration”.

Figure 7. Image spectrograms representing generative forest soundscapes across eight regions in Norway in May, 2022 that comprise the “Norway Forests: May” audio piece from Paper 5. The y-axis represents the panning of the audio, with the left-most panning containing audio from BirdNET detections in southern regions such as Kristiansand, and right-most panning for northern regions such as Finnmark. The x-axis represents how audio was sampled from BirdNET detections within 4-hour periods across the 2:32 piece. Figure excerpted from Paper 5 [48].

Indeed, research suggests that aesthetic appreciation of nature’s beauty is related to nature affiliation [152], [153], which in turn is a key driver of pro-environmental behaviors [98]. Scientific and artistic explorations of ecological data thus reinforce each other in a shared goal of conservation. Science provides the context for us to comprehend the magnitude and character of nature and its cycles, allowing us to appreciate nature “as nature” [120] and enhancing the aesthetic experience of nature and ecological art—analogue to knowledge of art history and techniques improving one’s aesthetic experience of a painting [118, p. 102]. In turn, art provides an open space for aesthetic exploration and personal relation that builds upon science but is not limited by its formal processes.

Still, biodiversity is in decline globally and the density and complexity of natural soundscapes has declined in parallel [33]. Future generations may rely more on artificial nature soundscapes to experience some of the physical [37], mental [36], and eudaimonic [38] benefits of nature. ML algorithms such as convolutional neural networks, variational autoencoders, diffusion, and generative adversarial networks are established methods of generating novel images and have been increasingly repurposed in the audio domain [154], [155], [156]. Generally, generative models compress media into a numerical vector in a high-dimensional latent space and by moving around this latent space, novel non-linear combinations of input media can be generated—presenting a method for generating infinite pseudo-nature based on nature-derived data. As virtual nature immersion has been shown to have some of the same beneficial effect as nature [41] (albeit limited), machine-derived nature may become an ameliorative aspect of the post-biodiversity future.

Paper 4 showcased a proof-of-concept nature soundscape generator to address the aforementioned needs of future generations for nature affiliation, considering current biodiversity collapse [4], [33]. We train a convolutional variational autoencoder (CVAE) in PyTorch on 1700 hour of global nature soundscapes—Norway, U.S., Borneo, Russia, China, and France—collected from open datasets such as Xeno-Canto, collaborators, and recordings from the Sound of Norway collected during this PhD. CVAEs excel at generative tasks in part due to their probabilistic nature and smooth latent spaces. They are trained to first encode a 2D image into two vectors, representing the location and variance of the input in the latent high dimensional space, then to decode the vectors back into the image with minimal loss. While the ease of implementation makes a CVAE appropriate for a case study, CVAEs suffer from loss in audio quality relative to other methods. Spectrogram images are lossy representations of audio, due to binning of frequency bands and loss of phase information [157], and the reconstruction of audio from these images, often performed using the Griffin-Lim algorithm [158], introduces significant noise. Here, this excess noise was reduced in a post-processing step. Still, we demonstrate that a relatively simple ML model can generate novel pseudo-nature soundscapes by interpolating across existing soundscapes, such as between a soundscape on a morning in rural New York and another at dawn in Shanghai, China (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Interpolations between decoded test set samples in a soundscape generation model's latent space across several ecosystems: between A) an evening in France and summer morning in New York, B) a winter morning in New York and spring dawn in China, and C) between two samples of the same dataset in Borneo during a summer afternoon. In this fashion, practically infinite high-dimensional combinations of environmental soundscapes can be generated. Excerpted from Paper 4 [47].

Many current state-of-the-art in generative audio models (in terms of audio quality) involve training directly on 1-D audio files instead of compressed representations like spectrograms or mel-frequency cepstral coefficients [156], [159]. A challenge of this approach is the understanding of temporal dependencies and audio context in extremely long input vectors—a second of raw audio recorded at a 44.1 KHz sample rate contains 44,100 data points, for example. One notable model, WaveNet, uses many stacked 1-D “causal” convolutional layers, in which previous timesteps inform the prediction of current one, to capture long-term dependencies in audio signal, avoid the high compute cost of recurrent neural networks, and generate realistic human voice reconstructions [159].

Despite such advancements in model capability, this techno-nature cannot fully replace what it is mimicking. In the seminal work *Biophilia*, EO Wilson invites the

reader to imagine themselves in the most visually pleasing possible natural landscape, except that when viewed closely, it is revealed to be a plastic human recreation that contains “no life whatsoever” [143]. His arguments from 1984 are surprisingly pertinent for modern considerations of digital nature:

“Artifacts are incomparably poorer than the life they are designed to mimic. They are only a mirror to our thoughts. To dwell on them exclusively is to fold inwardly over and over, losing detail at each translation, shrinking with each cycle, finally merging into the lifeless facade of which they are composed.” [143, p. 115]

ML can mimic nature by procedurally generating novel soundscapes [47], music [160], images [161], and visual art [162]. As increasingly seen in video games, even complete virtual environments may be procedurally generated [161], offering limitless novelty. The application of ML towards creative functions such as these, which are typically associated with human cognition, is associated with the concept of “artificial intelligence” (AI) [163]. Despite its ability to mimic human creativity, AI-generated media and nature inherent lacks materiality or context. In nature, a bird call has a purpose—alarm at a predator, seeking a mate, establishing territory [164]—and contributes to the broader context of the ecosystem. In contrast, the pseudo-natural soundscapes we generate in Paper 4 are arbitrary high-dimensional combinations of bird calls, insect buzzing, and wind, for example, that create novelty but are not tied to any ecological context.

In *Art in the After-Culture*, Ben Davis discusses an interactive AI art piece at the Metropolitan Museum of Art in New York City in 2019 in which the user may generate infinite novel pseudo-artifacts by exploring the latent space of an AI model trained on images of actual historical artifacts from the Museum’s collection. Davis argues that this process mines interesting surface-level visual aesthetics from the artifacts, but that it simultaneously drains the historical context that allows us to relate to them in a human way: “The results are weird and cool. They are also meaningless.” [118, p. 94]. Becoming inundated in such procedurally generated media and virtual environments threatens to accelerate existing trends of addiction to digital media (see [118, p. 107]), social atomization (see [118, p. 112]), and dissociation from nature [96], threatening our ability to collectively address our myriad ecoclimatic crises.

Chapter 5 – Conclusions and Future Work

5.1 – Conclusions

As technology advances and the amount of collected environmental data continues to increase [165], ML and automation will become increasingly useful for tackling our increasingly complex anthropogenic environmental problems [166]. As demonstrated in Topic 1 of this thesis in Yellowstone National Park and in Norwegian forests, automation has begun to enable semi-autonomous ecological monitoring systems to be deployed at large scales and relatively low cost. This is beginning to provide high spatiotemporal resolution data and ecological insights impossible with standard survey methods: measuring the *in-situ* impact of noise on animal vocalizations, the arrival phenology of migrating species, or near-real time national-scale biodiversity monitoring.

To be effective, this increasing capacity of ecological monitoring must be integrated with conservation policy and land management, analogous to how flood maps are commonly applied in flood and sea level rise risk management [167]. This policy integration has generally been a challenge thus far due to lack of political will, social pressure, and lack of integration of the scientific and policy communities, though there are successful examples [54], [80]. At the same time, technological advances in monitoring such as PAM and ML have the potential to fill current ecological monitoring gaps, providing more comprehensive evidence of anthropogenic effects on biodiversity and limiting the capacity for plausible deniability of environmental harm by industry, developers, and politicians.

Advances in technology that are revolutionizing ecological monitoring are also altering our states of mind and relationship with nature. Ironically, artificial nature may become increasingly present in parallel to decreasing biodiversity if significant steps in conservation and greenhouse gas reduction are not taken. Topic 2 of this thesis suggests that the role of technology in future ecological art is not to procedurally generate infinite hollow recreations of the natural world with ML. Instead, technology may assist our ability to tune to environmental hyperobjects [104]—such as climate change or entire ecosystems—by expanding our senses. Technology has certainly improved our ecological monitoring and modeling capacities, but further interplay between technologists, ecologists, policymakers, artists, and the public [166] is needed to develop the necessary scientific knowledge, broader public nature affiliation, and achieve concrete conservation goals. Ecologists may wish to share data with artists as a more common part of their practice, making their research more interpretable and relatable to the public and to policymakers—perhaps public funding for certain research projects could involve such science-art collaborations. Overall, I argue that an effective collective approach towards environmental stewardship is predicated upon both scientific understanding of nature as well as aesthetic appreciation and emotional affiliation with it.

5.2 Topic 1: Considerations and Future Work

The fact that citizen science surveys are spatiotemporally biased and breeding bird surveys are temporally limited exemplifies how PAM is especially applicable when simultaneous, continuous observation is needed, whether over large areas, in specific study areas, or in remote areas. This has many applications: supporting national or international biodiversity monitoring schemes, the tracking of biodiversity recovery in areas undergoing remediation, measuring biodiversity and noise pollution along a development gradient, or monitoring of long-term biodiversity or phenology in remote areas. PAM allows for the in-situ, in-absentia study of animal phenology at a fine scale difficult through manual surveys, such as population-wide effects of anthropogenic noise [45], building on the vast literature of research using manual survey that has demonstrated the harmful effects of anthropogenic noise on animals [2], [26], [30], [132]. Also possible is live observation of anomalous sounds such as gunshots [19] or human activity [168], relevant in conservation settings where poaching or logging is a threat. The potential for wide spatiotemporal coverage, as well as the absence of direct human surveyors, makes PAM useful for observing rare species with lower detectability [17], [169]. While species may have less available recordings, making training of automated ML detection models more difficult, such challenges may be offset through data augmentation or model architectures that specialize in few-shot learning [13].

Considerations for PAM survey design and implementation include the selection of appropriate sites, the need for expertise in data science and ML to train or apply models for detection, and meeting the power needs of detectors through sufficient solar power or battery storage—a challenge in Paper 3 where 25% of recorder uptime was lost due to power or equipment issues. Privacy concerns must also be considered when recording audio in areas where humans may travel, though these can be systemically detected and removed [168]. Although, as in Paper 3, end-users of ML models may not require access to raw data, and instead rely on species detections from validated ML models. Capturing near-live acoustic feeds from detectors also necessitates either satellite or cellular network connections which incur additional costs, as well as custom private or cloud-based server infrastructure to collect and process data. The need for real-time monitoring depends on application, and some initiatives, such as the Australian Acoustic Observatory which focuses on post hoc scientific analysis, may decide against it [16]. Overall, PAM enables new possibilities in conservation and ecological research but carries with it dependencies on expertise in sensors, programming, and ecology. However, powerful ML models such as BirdNET and pre-packaged PAM implementations (Bugg, Wildlife Acoustics, etc.) are becoming increasingly available and may ease implementation in organizations without technical prerequisites.

Considerations for ML include interpretability and explainability, with ML models having a black-box nature relative to parametric and statistical models [67]. The relatively complex nature of ML models somewhat hinders their communicability and may subsequently reduce trust from stakeholders [129]. Explainable AI methods

[129] can aid in model communicability in conservation contexts—one may identify important features in a model or use partial dependence plots to map how a single feature’s value changes a model output. However, feature importance methods can be sensitive to collinearity between features, and the most important feature for prediction accuracy may not always be the true causal feature [67]. ML methods are not a panacea, requiring human expert input for model validation, study design, interpretation of results, and acting on these results.

The research and literature review performed in Topic 1 demonstrates that PAM is an increasingly viable solution for ecological monitoring, research, and informed conservation efforts and that ML can help with automation and filling data gaps in ecology. However, it goes without saying that their must also be political and institutional will for effective and informed environmental policy for these methods to be applicable in conservation planning. There are few examples of ecological monitoring and modeling being effectively applied to government policy in the scientific literature [80], [170]. Historically, many conservation decisions have been made ad-hoc with “political convenience and opportunism driving the agenda” [170, p. 317] often in parallel with (or enabled by) large ecological data gaps, such as using incomplete species distribution maps while planning development projects [170]. In this context, ML and PAM can act as a force-multiplier for ecologists, filling data gaps [170] and contribute to sustainable development [54], [81], [94], [170]. Indeed, some groups, such as the Dutch ARISE program [171], are leveraging ML and PAM in an attempt to create comprehensive national accounting and monitoring of all multi-cellular species. Potential angles for increasing scientific impact are further integration of the research and policy communities [54], [170], [172], continued development of high-performing and transparent models [13], [129], [173], [174], and public-facing initiatives showcasing ecological data like dashboards [15] or collaborations with artists [175], [176] that increase ecological awareness and affiliation.

5.3 Topic 2: Considerations and Future Work

Scientific research and understanding of nature has been foundational for societal action on the climate and biodiversity crises [9], [53], [109]. Such knowledge also underlies our personal affiliation with nature (see [120]). However, it is apparent—based on society’s lacking response to these crises thus far—that science alone is insufficient on its own to facilitate large scale change. As these crises continue to develop, it is likely that art will increasingly incorporate ecological and climatic themes (see [102]), providing a space for exploring and integrating the complex emotions that arise from scientific knowledge of our environmental reality. Simple but effective art pieces such as *Ice Watch* [101] exemplify this possibility, but technology can also uniquely facilitate a fusion of art and science. In Paper 5, for example, we arrange PAM recordings across vast distances into a single sound art piece that allows the listener to experience an otherwise impossible scale of nature. Future work extending the idea of Paper 5 could involve spatial ecological sound art installations—compressing acoustic recordings of large geographies down to the size

of a space where visitors can physically move around (see Dunn *et al.* 2020 [125]), perhaps contributing to a deeper immersion and aesthetic relation with the ecological hyperobject the spatial recordings represent.

Technology allows for exciting new scientific and artistic methods, but just as scientists should be realistic about its limitations, artists should be mindful of its aesthetics, particularly regarding ML and AI. As famously stated by Marshall McLuhan, “the medium is the message” [177], and the message of AI in the creative arts often favors quantity and novelty over context and meaning [118, pp. 95–96]. The social, environmental, and artistic context in which one creates art matters in its appreciation and perceived emotional depth. Indeed, studies have demonstrated that while people may be fooled to thinking AI-generated art was made by a human, they value AI-labeled artworks less in terms of both aesthetic and monetary value, with their preferences possibly modulated by appreciation of human effort, meaning and narrative, and engagement in the artistic process [162], [178]. Artists incorporating AI into their work may wish to consider these aesthetic trade-offs.

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Paper 1:

Exploring the Spatiotemporal Influence of Climate on American Avian Migration with Random Forests

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Exploring the Spatiotemporal Influence of Climate on American Avian Migration with Random Forests

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Abstract

North and South American Birds have adapted to climatic and ecological patterns to inform their Spring and Fall migration timings. Temperature and precipitation patterns are shifting under anthropogenic climate change, causing downstream effects on plant flowering cycles, insect populations, and habitat availability. Understanding how these cues trigger migration could improve the effectiveness and timing of bird surveys, as well as informing habitat protection and creation efforts to lessen biodiversity loss due to climate change. Here, we employ a modeling approach to explore how climate spatiotemporally affects accuracy of predicting bird occurrence. Specifically, we train an ensemble of random forests on subsets of North and South American climate data to predict distributions of historical bird occurrence probability for passerine bird species in a North American forested region on eBird citizen science surveys from 2008-2018. We further investigate the relevance of each feature, region, and temporal lag for predicting the observed bird occurrence in a forested region in Northeast America, finding that both temperature and precipitation facilitate accurate prediction. For predicting species in October, when many passerines have begun their southward winter migration, we achieve more accurate predictions of bird occurrence using lagged, rather than current, climate features alone to predict communities in October. We also note significant higher random forest feature

importance for some lagged North American climate features than South American features. These results suggest that machine learning models may be useful for identifying spatiotemporal climatic cues that affect migratory behaviour. Lastly, we explore the application and limitations of random forests for prediction of future bird occurrence using 2021-2040 climate projections.

Introduction

Across the globe, birds undertake Spring migrations to breeding grounds and Fall migrations to winter in warmer climates. In the Western Hemisphere specifically, many bird species migrate northward from their winter homes in the Southeastern USA, the Caribbean, Mexico, and Central America to breeding grounds in the Northern forests of Canada and the United States each Spring, then again southward in the Fall (Jahn, Levey and Smith, 2004; Faaborg *et al.*, 2010). Bird species rely on climatic and ecological conditions such as temperature, pressure, precipitation, and food availability to trigger the timings of their migrations (Sutherland, 1998; Lemoine, Schaefer and Böhning-Gaese, 2007; Visser *et al.*, 2010; Koleček, Adamík and Reif, 2020) in addition to their endogenous rhythms (Marra *et al.*, 2005; Miller-Rushing *et al.*, 2008; Åkesson and Helm, 2020). However, these climatic and ecological triggers are shifting with climate change. In North America, these are projected to be characterized by warming of northern breeding regions, increased rainfall during Spring migration, and less rainfall in southern regions during non-breeding season (La Sorte *et al.*, 2017).

The broad effects of climate change on migrations have already been demonstrated: shifts to earlier Spring first arrival dates (Butler, 2003; Marra *et al.*, 2005; Mills, 2005; Faaborg *et al.*, 2010; Koleček, Adamík and Reif, 2020), smaller and more dispersed migratory cohorts (Miller-Rushing *et al.*, 2008), and a northward shifts in breeding grounds (La Sorte and Thompson,

2007). Bird species will have to adapt behavioral patterns more quickly to these habitat and climatic changes than has been done before anthropogenic climate change began (Faaborg *et al.*, 2010). However, the sensitivities to environmental and ecological cues have been genetically shaped by natural selection to correctly time behaviors such as egg laying to the availability of food, and species often over- or under-correct their timings (Visser, Holleman and Gienapp, 2006; Visser *et al.*, 2010). Understanding the fine details of these shifts in behavior is key to conserving biodiversity through the era of climate change. For example, the optimal times and places to conduct bird surveys may shift. Additionally, understanding the climatic and ecological factors underlying changing bird migration behavior could support habitat protection and creation.

Many studies have explored relationships between migration timings and climatic features through linear-based models. For example, linking warmer Spring temperatures in the Northeastern USA to earlier arrivals (Marra *et al.*, 2005; Miller-Rushing *et al.*, 2008), or demonstrating effects of local weather on autumn migration timing and stopovers (Shipley, Kelly and Frick, 2018; Haest *et al.*, 2019). The literature demonstrates clearly that changes in bird migratory behavior are correlated with, and to some degree explained by, the changing climate. Still, many papers (Marra *et al.*, 2005; Miller-Rushing *et al.*, 2008; Haest *et al.*, 2019) show trends from post-hoc analyses and do not directly use climatic features to predict how migratory patterns may change. Machine learning methods such as random forests can leverage non-linear and complex trends in ecological data (Cutler *et al.*, 2007; Hunt *et al.*, 2022) to model historical trends and make predictions of future behavior. Random forest models are high-performing, efficient to train compared to neural networks under limited data, have built-in feature importance metrics, and have been applied in ecological settings to relate climate and ecological features to biodiversity (Martín *et al.*, 2020; Hunt *et al.*, 2022) and animal movement.

Here, we seek to build upon the existing literature with a predictive modeling approach for species occurrence and migration patterns. Specifically, we use a random forest multi-regression to predict eBird ('eBird Basic Dataset', 2022) checklist occurrences of common migrating passerine species in a large North American forested region, using monthly averages of climate features (maximum temperature, minimum temperature, and precipitation) across North, Central, and South America as feature sets. By repeating this analysis across lags in the features, we explore which regions and times are critical for predicting species Spring arrival and Fall departure dates in North American forests. Through this approach, we make use of model error and feature importance metrics to explore which features, at which times and places, are most useful for prediction of migration. We demonstrate that random forest regressors can accurately predict passerine species occurrence, even when presented with limited training data. We also show that lagged temperature and precipitation features are as predictive, and often more predictive, of species occurrence probability than non-lagged features. Finally, we train a random forest regression model on historical data, then project future checklist occurrences using several climate models projections averaged from 2021-2040, comparing our results to the general literature consensus of earlier species Spring arrival times and later Fall departure times due to climate change. The data and Python notebooks required to run these analyses are available online (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7769656).

Methods

eBird Data

We used the eBird Basic Dataset from 2008-2018 ('eBird Basic Dataset', 2022) to derive the monthly occurrence rate of bird species across surveys in our study area. The dataset consists of checklists of observed species from citizen scientists, representing an "encounter rate" metric

for each target species, which can be thought of as the product of that species' detectability and occurrence probability (Johnston *et al.*, 2021). We implement several data pre-processing steps to limit spatiotemporal variability in species detectability to create an "apparent distribution" (Johnston *et al.*, 2021) of encounter rate that resembles actual occurrence probability as much as possible: we restrict surveys to forested areas, only consider the most common migrating passerine species, and drop high-effort surveys. To account for increases in eBird usage throughout the study period, we also subsample surveys (Fink *et al.*, 2020) annually.

Checklists were first filtered to our study area, the Level 2 Ecoregion "Atlantic Highlands" within the Level 1 "Northern Forests" Ecoregion (Fig. 1) ('Level I and II Ecoregions of North America', 2010). These Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) Ecoregions seek to aggregate areas of similar plant and animal species, as well as abiotic characteristics such as water availability (Omernik and Griffith, 2014). The "Northern Forests" ecoregion is characterized by extensive boreal forests and lakes (*Ecological regions of North America: toward a common perspective*, 1997), as well as extensive coverage by eBird surveys. This spatial aggregation allowed us to limit the number of climate predictor variables in our random forest models and thus more easily study the temporal effects of regional climate on migration.

Checklists were further processed according to methods recommended by Johnston shown to improve the performance of species occupancy and detection models when using eBird data, especially in models with large survey sample sizes (Johnston *et al.*, 2021). Specifically, we included only 'complete' checklists, removing any surveys where an unknown species was observed, and thus retaining information on species absence. Surveys with very high effort, specifically those lasting over three hours and traveling more than 5 km, as well as area counts, were excluded to retain spatial information of observations. Group surveys, which contain redundant checklists, were condensed to a single checklist.

We next limited the species of interest to the 50 most common passerine species, as such birds in general have a lower body mass and higher cold sensitivity, which can induce migratory behaviors (Dawson, Marsh and Yacoe, 1983). Of these species, we filtered down to 41 species (mean observations: 3,571, std: 2,044) (Table S1) which are either short-distance or long-distance migrants rather than resident species, based on distribution maps from Birds of the World (Billerman *et al.*, 2022) and expert opinion. To further refine our analysis to only forested regions, we filtered out all checklists with less than 50% surrounding tree cover based on 100m resolution tree cover density data ('Copernicus 2018 100m Forest Cover Fraction', 2020). From 2008 until 2018, the number of annual surveys in eBird has greatly increased. To avoid bias in inferred species richness in later years which have a greater number of surveys, we randomly subsampled 1601 surveys at the annual scale, the number of surveys in 2008 after filtering for forest cover and survey type (Fig. S1). We then calculated the percentage of surveys on which each species appears on a monthly scale to create our target features.

Climate Data

To study historical patterns in migration and climate, we utilized WorldClim monthly historical raster data (Harris *et al.*, 2014) downscaled with WorldClim 2.1 (Fick and Hijmans, 2017) for monthly minimum temperature, maximum temperature, and precipitation at 2.5 minute spatial resolution across North and South America. The raster data were averaged into EPA Level 1 Ecoregions for North and South America (Fig. 1a) that fall within typical migration pathways for birds that spend their breeding season in the eBird study region. Features were then individually normalized by setting a mean of 0 and scaling features to unit variance. Each of the three feature sets (maximum temperature, minimum temperature, and precipitation) had a total of 15 features per month, from eight North American Ecoregions and seven South American

Ecoregions. One feature set containing all three climate features was also created, with 45 features in total.

Figure 1: Map of targeted EPA Ecoregions and eBird survey locations. a) North and South American Level 1 Ecoregions for averaging of climate variables. b) The eBird study region Ecoregion 5.3, a subset of Level 1 Ecoregion 5 (NA5), outlined in light green with individual eBird survey coordinates in black. c) Data flow through random forest model ensembles. Monthly climate features are aggregated to the Level 1 Ecoregion spatial scale and monthly eBird species occurrence fractions across checklists are calculated for the Ecoregion 5.3 study region. An ensemble of ten models is trained and tested for each month and climate feature combination to predict checklist occurrence fractions, and the results of the ensemble are then averaged.

Similarly, to generate projected climate features, we utilized WorldClim monthly projected data from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) (Fick and Hijmans, 2017), aggregated and averaged to the same EPA Level 1 Ecoregions. The CMIP6 framework forms the standard for international climate assessments, such as those from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (Eyring *et al.*, 2016) and includes an ensemble of climate models from various research groups that rely on common historical training data. For each CMIP6 model, we also tested several radiative forcing pathways, dubbed the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) (O'Neill *et al.*, 2016), which compared the effects of various greenhouse gas emissions scenarios. Due to our use of a standard random forest regressor, which averages across previously-seen training samples to make predictions and cannot extrapolate, our projections of species occurrence fall within the bounds of observed species occurrences on eBird checklists from 2008-2018. Still, in order to avoid projecting species occurrence rates in radically different climatic conditions, we limited our study to the 2021-2040 averaged WorldClim datasets. This consists of the mean projected monthly minimum temperature, maximum temperature, and precipitation from 2021 to 2040. We used four CMIP6 models available from WorldClim which performed best on tests comparing probability distributions of projections to historical observations and the regularity of climate fluctuations (Papalexiou *et al.*, 2020).

Analysis of Historical Avian Migration

We trained Random Forest regressors on the historical climate features to predict the eBird checklist target features (Fig. 1c). Twelve ensembles of models were trained in total, one for prediction of eBird checklist occurrences in each month of the year. This separate training of models for each month of the year and lag on the climate feature dataset enabled us to study seasonal patterns in the error rates and feature importance. Each ensemble of models consists

of ten 1000-tree Random Forest models trained with varying 30:70 test-train splits across the ten years of data being studied (2009-2018). For example, the first model was trained on 2009, 2010, and 2011 data, and tested on 2012-2018 data, the second model was trained on 2010, 2011, and 2012 data, and tested on 2013-2018 and 2009 data, and so forth. Each model is trained on 7 years x 15 aggregated climate features, or 7 x 45 when using all temperature and precipitation features. This process was then repeated while lagging the climate features from one to six months. For example, the climate features from March were used to train models to predict the checklist occurrences in April, and so forth.

From each group of ten models (an ensemble), we recorded the mean and variance of the test set predictions and mean absolute errors for all species. We also extracted random forest feature importance for each climate feature and Ecoregion. The features ranking highest in importance were those which best split the distribution of target features across all nodes in the decision trees. For a regression problem such predicting checklist occurrences, this decrease in impurity is related to the reduction of variance that each feature provides when splitting training set samples. These forest importance metrics are relative, and sum to one ('Feature Importances with a Forest of Trees', 2023). As these ensembles of models generate distributions of error and feature importance, we were able to compare their performances in Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests. These statistical tests can evaluate whether one distribution is significantly greater or less than another, allowing us to test whether certain features facilitate better model performance based on their errors, or if certain groups of features have higher importance.

Projections of Avian Migration Shifts

We trained scikit-learn random forest multi-regression models (each with 1,000 trees) on the combined data set of 45 climate features aggregated to the Ecoregion scale (minimum temperature, maximum temperature, and precipitation) to predict the target eBird data from 2009-2015. Validation was performed on 2016-2018 data (FIG. S4). We then used this model to project on the 2021-2040 monthly average climate projections from the four CMIP6 models (EC-Earth3-Veg, INM-CM4-8, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, and GISS-E2-1-H.) and four SSP projections (SSP 1, 2, 3, and 5). As with the historical ensemble of models, a separate model was trained to predict each month of the year. Projected species-wise shifts in monthly occurrence probability were calculated by subtracting the mean monthly eBird checklist occurrences (2009-2018) from the mean projected occurrences for each of the four CMIP6 models and four projections.

Results

We found accurate per-species predictions of eBird checklists for the 41 passerines studied (Fig. 2a) were made with monthly mean climate data (Fig. 2d) as well as with lagged climate data up to 6 months (Fig. 2f). Average monthly errors in predictions were generally low across all months and across climate features, ranging from 1.7 to 3.8 percent error in eBird checklist occurrence fraction averaged across all species (Fig. 3, SI Fig 2), with higher errors in the Spring and Summer months when species richness was also higher. We noted a trend in the mean annual error across species where the model tended to under-predict species occurrence fraction in earlier years and over-predict species occurrence fraction in later years (Fig 3a-d). This pattern in error followed a trend in the underlying eBird data; on average, each species in the study occurred on 2.6% fewer eBird checklists from 2009 to 2018 (Fig. 2c), a trend apparent for most species (Fig. 2e, 2g).

Figure 2: Aggregated climate data supports accurate predictions of eBird species checklist occurrences - a) List of 41 common migrating passerine bird species observed in forested areas of the study region, representing the y-axis of the following heatmaps. b) Actual eBird checklist occurrence fractions for all species. c) Mean annual eBird checklist occurrence across all species (blue) and the mean annual error in occurrence fraction predictions (red) across all species. d) The Random Forest-predicted eBird checklist occurrence fractions for all species utilizing all available climate variables (minimum temperature, maximum temperature, and precipitation), e) eBird checklists minus the predicted checklists using current climate feature sets, showing over-predictions in blue and under-predictions in red, f) predicted eBird checklist occurrences utilizing all climate variables lagged by six months, and g) eBird checklists minus the predicted checklists using six month lagged climate variables.

Figure 3 illustrates the accuracy of the random forest ensembles for prediction of species occurrence fractions, but also how the temporal trends in the underlying eBird features impacted model performance. The model increasingly tended to overpredict individual species checklist

occurrence towards later years in the analysis (Figs. 3c, 3d). Following this, the derived species richness was also increasingly over-predicted (Figs. 3a, 3b). Figure 3e and 3f focus on April and October specifically, as these months are transitory periods between breeding and winter seasons (Fig. 2b) when migratory species are arriving and departing our study area. We noted higher volatility and no apparent trend in model error for April (Fig. 3e). In October, however, the lowest error occurred when climate feature sets were lagged by one to three months (Fig. 3f).

We performed Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests on the distributions of errors across the model ensembles to determine whether the lower error of these lagged datasets was significant. After correcting for multiple hypotheses, we found that lagging climate features for two and three months produced significant reductions in model MAE for predicting eBird checklist occurrences in October ($p=0.00981$) (Table S2). No such significant changes in error were found for lagged datasets in April. We applied Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests between distributions of random forest feature importance of the North and South American ecoregions (Fig. S5) to determine if the model was identifying relevant regional features. For predicting checklist occurrences in October in our northeastern study region, we found that North American climate features were significantly more important only at a lag of 3 ($p < 0.001$) (Table S2). No significant effects were seen for importance in predicting April occurrences.

Figure 3: Model predictions across years reveal underlying shifts in eBird species occurrence and strength of lagged climate data for predictions. a) 2009 and b) 2018 eBird species richness versus mean and standard deviation of predicted species richness across the model ensemble. Species richness shown includes all species appearing on more than two percent of actual and predicted eBird checklists. c) 2009 and d) 2018 eBird ground truth versus predicted checklist occurrence fraction, showing mean and standard deviation of predictions across the model ensemble. e) Average random forest mean absolute test set errors by month of feature lag for April and f) October across all species and climate features.

By training on the 2008-2018 eBird checklists with all climate features and testing on CMIP6 climate projections (making broad assumptions of no change in habitat or species abundance), we projected higher positive shifts in checklist occurrence probability for April through August (ranging from 0.36% to 0.75%), with less change projected for Fall months (ranging from 0.011 to 0.19%) (Fig. 4a). We found an increase in species occurrence probability across models projected for 25 of 41 species in April (mean: 0.80%), 15 species having a projected decrease

(mean: -0.36%), and one species with no change (Fig. 4b). Results were more mixed for October, with projected occurrence probability increases for 20 of 41 species (mean: 0.67%), decreases for 19 (mean: -0.46%), and no change for two species (Fig. 4c). In contrast to the variation within eBird training data, the variance of occurrence probability for all species was effectively zero across all four CMIP6 models and four SSP projections tested, indicating that the random forest model consistently reached the bounds of known distributions of checklist occurrences across the available climate training data.

Figure 4: Projections of eBird checklist occurrences from 2021-2040 show earlier Spring occurrence probability for passerine species - a) Violin plot showing mean projected shifts of occurrence probability for 41 passerine species in 2021-2040 compared to historical eBird monthly means from 2008-2018 in Ecoregion 5.3 b) April and c) October per-species difference between mean historical eBird occurrence probability and mean 2021-2040 projected occurrence probability.

Discussion

In this section, we begin by highlighting the effectiveness of aggregated climate features from both North and South America in accurately predicting eBird checklist occurrence probability for 41 passerine species in our North American forest study region, as well as species richness (depicted in Fig. 2b and Fig. 3a, b). Importantly, the accuracy of our predictions remained consistent regardless of the specific climate variable chosen as a training feature (as illustrated in Fig. 3e, 3f, and Fig. S2). Additionally, combining multiple climate features resulted in reduced variability in prediction error (as indicated in Fig. 3e and f). Furthermore, we observed that the trend in mean annual model error closely mirrored the trend in mean annual checklist occurrence over time across all species (as shown in Fig. 2c). This alignment in error trends might be attributed to underlying patterns of decreasing biodiversity and total bird counts observed during our study period, a phenomenon that has also been documented in previous studies (Anders and Post, 2006; Sauer and Link, 2011). It's worth noting that potential errors could also arise from systematic shifts in the accuracy of the underlying eBird data. However, we attempted to mitigate this risk by using randomly selected complete checklists, as recommended by Johnston et al. (2021).

During October, a period when species are actively migrating southward from our study region (as depicted in Fig. 3a), we observed a notable reduction in prediction error when climate features were lagged by two or three months, in comparison to using current climate features (as illustrated in Fig. 3b, Table S2). The results suggest that our model ensembles may be effectively capturing delayed temporal patterns in climate that influence migratory departure. Furthermore, in October, the random forest analysis highlighted that North American climate features were significantly more influential than South American features at a lag of three months, indicating that the model may be discerning spatial climate cues contributing to

migratory behavior. Conversely, in April, when birds are arriving in our Northern study area from their Southern wintering grounds (as shown in Fig. 2b), the model did not identify any statistically significant temporal or spatial differences in prediction error or feature importance.

These findings align with existing research that highlights the influence of time lagged effects of climate on migration triggers. For instance, (Visser, Holleman and Gienapp, 2006; Evans *et al.*, 2019). Our projections of bird species from 2021-2040 were not designed to model future changes in biodiversity and population abundance. Instead they serve the purpose of exploring how bird species might respond if sudden shifts in climatic conditions were to occur in the near future, such as within the next year. Essentially, we aimed to uncover insights from historical climate and bird migration patterns that could shed light on potential future trends. Furthermore, it's important to note that our approach utilizes a random forest model architecture. As a result, our projections of future species occurrence probability remain constrained within the bounds of the historical training data, rendering them inherently conservative. These projections do not account for factors like changes in land-use and development (La Sorte *et al.*, 2017), alterations in the timing of resource availability related to insects and flowering plants (Sparks, Jeffree and Jeffree, 2000; Keatley *et al.*, 2002; Visser, Holleman and Gienapp, 2006; Rawal *et al.*, 2015; Evans *et al.*, 2019), or shifts in inter-species competition (Freeman 2022), all of which affect bird populations and distributions. These aspects are known to exert significant influences on bird populations and distributions.

Despite these limitations, we were still able to discern potential future trends in the timing of bird arrivals and departures, consistent with existing literature and empirical research. Notably, our findings indicate an increased occurrence of species arriving in North American forests during the spring (as depicted in Fig. 4b). However, the trends for autumn months were more varied (as shown in Fig. 4c), aligning with previous studies (Haest 2019, Mills 2005). Several aspects of our results suggest a higher sensitivity to climate and greater volatility in the Spring migration

than the Fall migration. This includes the higher test set error observed in April compared to October (Fig. 3e, 3f) and the more pronounced and extensive shifts in projected future species occurrences in April and May than in Fall months (as displayed in Figs. 4a, 4b and 4c). It is important to note that test set error for the climate projection model exceeded the training set error (covering the period from 2008 to 2015) and displayed an upward trend from 2016 to 2018 (as presented in Fig. S6, 7). This trend culminated in a monthly maximum mean absolute error of 5.3% for August 2018.

The monthly scale of data resolution and the resulting small dataset size in this analysis constrained our ability to employ more deep learning techniques, like recurrent neural networks, which potentially could capture nuanced temporal influences of climate on migration. Nonetheless, the utilization of random forests decision trees offered several advantages, including built-in feature importance methods and the ability to confine future predictions within the bounds of the training dataset. This contrasts with simpler models such as multiple linear regression, which might produce projections outside the historical range.

For future research, there are several avenues to explore for enhancing our understanding of bird migration in relation to climate. One promising direction involves improving the temporal and spatial resolution of the climate datasets, which could enable machine learning models to provide a more comprehensive view of climate influence on migration patterns. Additionally, focusing on factors related to population abundance might yield valuable insights, particularly in light of observed decreases in bird populations. Furthermore, incorporating other climate features that are known to affect migrations such as wind speed and direction (as highlighted by Haest 2019) could contribute to a more comprehensive model. Finally, the inclusion of indices derived from satellite data such as normalized difference vegetation and water indices, which are associated with food availability and drought conditions (as mentioned by Alessandrini et al.,

2022; Hunt et al., 2022), could provide a more holistic understanding of the ecological factors impacting bird migrations.

Conclusions

In this study, we present a modeling approach to identify spatiotemporal climate features that influence bird migratory behavior. Our results demonstrate that random forest models trained on these features accurately predicted eBird checklist occurrence probability throughout the year in a northern forested region. Our findings indicate that lagged feature sets were more effective in predicting passerine species occurrence probability in October compared to current climate conditions. The models also assigned greater spatiotemporal importance to North American features over South American features in October, coinciding with the southward migration of species to their wintering sites.

Furthermore, we explored potential future trends in migratory behavior using mean climate projections from CMIP6 for the period 2021-2040. Our results suggest an increased occurrence probability in Spring and Summer months, but a reduced effect in the Fall and Winter. These findings aligned with existing, supporting the hypothesis of a shifting of migratory timings with climate change, characterized by earlier spring arrivals and later autumn departures. Our pilot tests demonstrate that thorough investigation into model performance and feature importance within machine learning models can contribute to our understanding of complex ecological processes.

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Author Contributions

IAB led manuscript writing and methodology design and ran the analyses. VB, MP, KR, and SS advised on methodology design and research questions and made significant contributions to the manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved the manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Supplemental Information

Figure S1 - Monthly species richness for migrating passerine species (left) and number of sampled eBird surveys per month (right).

Figure S2 - Monthly mean absolute error of eBird checklist occurrence predictions by month of feature lag.

eBird Climate Projection Model - Train and Test Error

Figure S3 - Random Forest training set (2008-2015) and test set (2016-2018) error for climate projection model

eBird Climate Projection Model - Monthly Mean Absolute Error

Figure S4 - Random forest training set (2008-2015) and test set (2016-2018) monthly mean absolute error across all species for climate projection model

Figure S5 - Kernel Density Estimation of random forest feature importance for predicting eBird checklist occurrence in a,b) October and c,d) April. Distributions are split into North (n=45) and South American (n=24) ecoregions and include model importance for each climate variable (max temperature, minimum temperature, and precipitation).

Table S1 – Observation count per species across eBird checklists

Species	Observations
American Robin	10685
American Goldfinch	8637
Song Sparrow	8510
Common Yellowthroat	5881
Red-eyed Vireo	5585
Red-winged Blackbird	5491
Eastern Phoebe	5214
Gray Catbird	5184
Dark-eyed Junco	4914
White-throated Sparrow	4602
Chipping Sparrow	4464
Ovenbird	4409
Cedar Waxwing	4405
Yellow-rumped Warbler	4004
Common Grackle	3762
Black-throated Green Warbler	3371
Tree Swallow	3295
American Redstart	3177
Chestnut-sided Warbler	3011
Black-and-white Warbler	2954
Hermit Thrush	2933
Veery	2827
Blue-headed Vireo	2512
Yellow Warbler	2511
Eastern Bluebird	2418
Purple Finch	2303
Black-throated Blue Warbler	2229
Scarlet Tanager	2200
Eastern Wood-Pewee	2144
Golden-crowned Kinglet	2099
Swamp Sparrow	2067
Brown-headed Cowbird	1988
Baltimore Oriole	1987
Rose-breasted Grosbeak	1974
Eastern Towhee	1933
Wood Thrush	1911
Magnolia Warbler	1900
House Wren	1837
Blackburnian Warbler	1787
Barn Swallow	1764
Ruby-crowned Kinglet	1689

Table S2 – Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistical test results comparing distributions of model mean absolute errors for eBird checklist occurrences in a) October and b) April. Model ensemble errors across several lags of the climate datasets (max temperature, minimum temperature, precipitation) are compared to model errors with no lag in the datasets. P-values determine if the lagged results are in a distribution that is significantly less than the no lag error distribution (see Figure S7). A similar process is applied on the distributions of random forest feature importance (see Figure S8) to determine if North American climate features (n=45) are significantly more important than South American climate features (n=24) for predicting eBird checklist occurrence in c) October and d) April. Multiple hypothesis corrections are applied to each p-value to correct for multiple experiments in each month, P-values are multiplied by three for the MAE tests and by four for the importance tests.

a) October MAE – K-S Test (n=30)			
Lag	KS Statistic	p-value	Corrected p-value
0	0	1	---
1	0.333	0.0354	0.106

2	0.433	0.00327	0.00981
3	0.433	0.00327	0.00981

b) April MAE – K-S Test (n=30)			
Lag	KS Statistic	p-value	Corrected p-value
0	0	1	---
1	0.267	0.12	0.360
2	0.0333	0.968	2.904
3	0.267	0.12	0.12

c) October Importance – K-S Test (n=(45,24))			
Lag	KS Statistic	p-value	Corrected p-value
0	0.208	0.324	1.296
1	0.232	0.255	1.020
2	0.0476	0.916	2.748
3	0.589	0.000195	0.000780

d) April Importance – K-S Test (n=(45,24))			
Lag	KS Statistic	p-value	Corrected p-value
0	0.0714	0.842	3.296
1	0.25	0.206	0.824
2	0.244	0.224	0.896
3	0.119	0.666	2.664

Paper 2:

Snowmobile noise alters bird vocalization patterns during winter and pre-breeding season

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*Benjamin Cretois and Ian Avery Bick contributed equally to this work.

Contribution Statement:

Devised and implemented bucketing methodology to analyze temporal relationships between engine noise and avian vocalization phenology. Drafted half of the manuscript, along with Benjamin Cretois.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Snowmobile noise alters bird vocalization patterns during winter and pre-breeding season

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Abstract

1. Noise pollution poses a significant threat to ecosystems worldwide, disrupting animal communication and causing cascading effects on biodiversity. In this study, we focus on the impact of snowmobile noise on avian vocalizations during the non-breeding winter season, a less-studied area in soundscape ecology.
2. We developed a pipeline relying on deep learning methods to detect snowmobile noise and applied it to a large acoustic monitoring dataset collected in Yellowstone National Park.
3. Our results demonstrate the effectiveness of the snowmobile detection model in identifying snowmobile noise and reveal an association between snowmobile passage and changes in avian vocalization patterns.
4. Snowmobile noise led to a decrease in the frequency of bird vocalizations during mornings and evenings, potentially affecting winter and pre-breeding behaviours such as foraging, predator avoidance and successfully finding a mate. However, we observed a recovery in avian vocalizations after detection of snowmobiles during mornings and afternoons, indicating some resilience to sporadic noise events.
5. *Synthesis and applications:* Our findings emphasize the need to consider noise impacts in the non-breeding season and provide valuable insights for natural resource managers to minimize disturbance and protect critical avian habitats. The deep learning approach presented in this study offers an efficient and accurate means of analysing large-scale acoustic monitoring data and contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the cumulative impacts of multiple stressors on avian communities.

KEYWORDS

anthropogenic noise, biodiversity conservation, bird vocalizations, deep learning, soundscape ecology

Benjamin Cretois and Ian Avery Bick contributed equally to this work.

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1 | INTRODUCTION

Noise pollution is a growing concern for ecosystems worldwide. Anthropogenic noise from sources such as traffic can mask biophony (i.e. the cumulative non-human sound produced by living organisms in a given habitat), disrupting animal communication and causing cascading effects on habitat availability (Bayne et al., 2008; Ware et al., 2015), reproductive success (Naguib, 2013; Schroeder et al., 2012) and biodiversity (Ware et al., 2015). Passive acoustic monitoring methods are uniquely suited to study such interplay between biophony and anthrophony, as they enable cost-effective collection of soundscape data over long periods of time and wide geographic areas. However, this wealth of data creates a need for automated techniques to identify and separate target sounds such as vocalizations from species of interest or anthropogenic noises. Deep learning methods are well suited for this task and have been shown to successfully identify vocalizing animal species (Kahl et al., 2021; Poupard et al., 2022; Stowell et al., 2019), human voices (Cretois et al., 2022), and engine noises (Espinosa et al., 2021) from audio recordings. By using multiple automated detectors in parallel, one may efficiently detect and study relationships between anthropogenic sounds and animal vocalizations.

Previous acoustic ecology studies have demonstrated the complex effects of anthropogenic noise on bird species: reduced body condition (Ware et al., 2015), increased vigilance and lower food intake (Quinn et al., 2006), increased call duration (Courter et al., 2020), reduced nest visitation (Naguib, 2013) and habitat quality reduction (Ware et al., 2015). Most studies have focused on chronic effects of noise which have persisted for weeks, months or years. Previous studies that have explored immediate effects of noise on wildlife, such as for snowmobile and aircraft noise events (Borkowski et al., 2006; Lawler et al., 2004; Maier et al., 1998; Vincelette et al., 2021), have relied on direct observation or manual sound annotation, requiring many work hours and potentially limiting temporal scope. Deep learning techniques have made it possible to analyse large amounts of data for event identification and classification (Stowell, 2022). This presents an opportunity to study the impact of anthropogenic noise on avian vocalizations at both a higher temporal resolution and with a larger temporal and geographic scope.

Most literature on noise impacts to birds specifically considers breeding season vocalizations (Oden et al., 2020; Shannon et al., 2016), while impacts of noise during the non-breeding winter and pre-breeding seasons remain understudied (though see Mullet et al., 2016; Quinn et al., 2022) despite the non-breeding season comprising a substantial portion of avian life history (Faaborg et al., 2010). Birds engage in a myriad of critical behaviours during the non-breeding season, such as foraging, establishing territories and forming social bonds, which could be perceptibly influenced by noise disturbances. For instance, noise might mask acoustic signals vital for social interactions or could potentially divert foraging birds from optimal habitats due to auditory disruptions (Dominoni et al., 2020). Because noise and more specifically anthropogenic

noise such as engine noises may act as a threat multiplier in combination with other stressors like habitat loss and climate change, it is critical to better understand the extent of the influence of anthropogenic winter noise on avian vocalizations. Automated detection models for anthropogenic winter noise (such as engine noise from snowmobiles) can facilitate efficient assessments of avian responses to noise and inform natural resource management strategies.

Reliable automated detection of snowmobiles in particular presents unique challenges due to both a lack of available training data for deep learning models and confounding noise sources in the soundscape. Wind noise is a particular issue, as it introduces low-frequency acoustic energy that may be mislabeled as an engine (Juodakis & Marsland, 2021). While studies have mapped the prevalence of snowmobile noise in American wilderness areas (Mullet & Morton, 2021) and explored potential for masking of bird calls (Keyel et al., 2018), little work has been done to measure direct impacts of snowmobiles on bird vocalizations (National Park Service, 2013).

Yellowstone National Park, located in the western United States in Wyoming, is a unique place spanning 8900 km² where wildlife coexists with anthropogenic noise, including along roads. Snowmobiling is a popular recreational activity in the park, attracting thousands of visitors annually. Between mid-December and mid-March, the park's roads are only accessible via such "oversnow" vehicles such as snowmobiles and snowcoaches. Snowmobiles often generate more noise than car engines (Daily & Raap, 2002; Menge et al., 2002) and have been shown to instigate vigilance, travel, and occasional flight responses in Yellowstone's elk and bison, especially when animals were closer to roads (Borkowski et al., 2006). Noise associated with oversnow vehicles is an important management concern in the park and noise impacts have been routinely measured via acoustic monitoring (Burson, 2018). To manage and mitigate oversnow vehicle impacts, Yellowstone implemented a series of environmental impact statements and environmental assessments, culminating in the adoption of the current Winter Use Plan in 2013 (National Park Service, 2013). However, it is unclear how snowmobile noise impacts the park's diverse winter avifauna such as owls, raptors, and overwintering songbirds such as bohemian waxwings, dark-eyed juncos, red-breasted nuthatches, and mountain chickadees (National Audubon Society, 2020; National Park Service, 2013; Walker et al., 2020).

In landscapes where recreation and wildlife conservation may present conflicting priorities and legal challenges (Dustin & Schneider, 2004), a rigorous methodology is necessary to measure and assess noise impacts. Acoustic monitoring of winter soundscapes provides one avenue for evaluating noise impacts, but it can be challenging to efficiently identify target noise and sound events in large audio datasets. Addressing these obstacles may offer novel insights on the impacts of snowmobile noise on non-breeding birds and support natural resource managers in making informed decisions that balance recreation and conservation.

In this study, we developed a methodology for assessing the short-term effects of noise impacts from snowmobiles on the winter and pre-breeding avian community, providing a snapshot into the

immediate alterations and responses in their acoustic behaviours. We used acoustic monitoring data to pursue the following objectives: (1) train a deep learning model to detect snowmobile noise, (2) test the snowmobile detector on a large winter acoustic monitoring dataset collected at Yellowstone National Park and (3) assess the methodology for investigating how bird vocalization frequency reacts to and recovers from snowmobile noise, using the Yellowstone dataset as a case study.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Data collection

2.1.1 | Dataset 1: Training and validation of the model

To obtain data for training and validation, we compiled three audio datasets (Figure 1-1). (1) During the winter of 2022 in Bymarka near Trondheim, Norway, an Audiomoth (model 1.1.0) was placed

1.20 m above the ground in the middle of a 150×150 m skiing play area for children. A single 4-stroke snowmobile (Lynx Yeti ACE 900) transited the area at an approximate speed of 10 km/h. The audio also contains singing birds, people talking and children playing. (2) The data from Hattfjelldal commune in Nordland, Norway, were recorded with an Audiomoth 1.1.0 in March and April 2022 at four sites along snowmobile tracks. Snowmobile traffic was recorded for a few hours at each site. (3) A third dataset from previous work gathered audio recordings of passing snowmobiles with different speeds and engine types (Gjestland & Haukland, 2017). All files were analysed with Raven Pro 1.6. Some were discarded because of bad quality or clipping. No permit was required to collect these datasets.

The recordings contained both segments with snowmobile and without snowmobile passages and were therefore manually reviewed and labelled. All time intervals where a snowmobile was audible were categorized as “snowmobile”. All time intervals where no snowmobile was audible were categorized as “background”. In total, the training and validation sets were composed of 4 and 33 h of snowmobile sounds and background sounds, respectively.

FIGURE 1 Workflow of the method.

2.1.2 | Dataset 2: Model testing and use in a passive acoustic monitoring scenario

To evaluate the performance of our classifier we used a large acoustic dataset composed of continuous recordings (i.e. no time gaps between files) collected at 20 sites in Yellowstone National Park. Data collection sites occurred in the vicinity of two roadside locations (Madison Junction and near Lewis Lake) and one destination area (Old Faithful) (see Supplementary Map 1). Recordings occurred during the winter use season spanning from December 15th until March 15th and between the years 2008 and 2017. Because of the variation in sampling protocol at each site, there are inter-site differences in the time range (i.e. some sites containing acoustic data spanning from 2009 up to 2017 while other sites containing only a year of acoustic data) and in the length of the recorded files (i.e. some files containing about 15s of audio while others containing about 12h of audio; Burson, 2009, 2018). In total the Yellowstone dataset comprised approximately 43,000h (equivalent to 1791 days) of audio collected through passive acoustic monitoring. For simplicity, we refer to this dataset as the Yellowstone dataset hereafter. Data was collected in accordance with Yellowstone Research Permits (Burson, 2009, 2018).

The test dataset was composed of 36h of randomly sampled data from the Yellowstone dataset that we manually labelled using Raven Pro (Figure 1-3). All time intervals where a snowmobile was audible have been noted. In addition, if other audible engine sounds such as helicopter noise, aircraft noise, and car noise were detected, they were labelled as well. Using the model on the test dataset allowed us to infer the model's performance metrics including precision, recall and F1 score.

The portion of the Yellowstone dataset not included in model testing was used to study the impact of snowmobiles on avian vocalization. No manual tagging was available and it was unknown whether the audio files contained snowmobile noises or bird vocalization.

2.2 | Snowmobile detection model architecture and training

To construct a model efficient at classifying snowmobile noises we used a ResNext model (i.e. Residual network that leverages attention layers) that had been pre-trained on AudioSet as feature extractor (Guzhov et al., 2021). The ResNext model architecture was chosen as the incorporation of both residual connections and attention mechanisms facilitates the model efficiently learning relevant features from the audio spectrograms, thereby potentially improving its robustness and generalization to diverse and challenging acoustic environments, compared to other architectures. We appended a final fully connected layer with two output neurons. Based on a hyperparameter search using Ray.tune (Liaw et al., 2018), the base ResNext model was then fine-tuned on our training data using the cross entropy loss function, a learning rate of 0.005, and a

batch size of 32. The model was trained for a total of 21 epochs as we set an early stopping on the validation loss (i.e. if the validation loss increases after reaching a minimum the model stops training) (Figure 1-2).

The training data was resampled at 44.1kHz to properly represent the broad spectrum of frequencies emitted by snowmobiles, which can span from low to high frequencies. We split the data into non overlapping 3s segments to ensure that the model had sufficient temporal context to identify and learn the characteristic acoustic patterns of snowmobile noises. Then, we transformed the 3s segments into a log-power spectrogram using a Fast Fourier Transform window size of 46ms (2048 samples at 44.1kHz) and a hop length of 13ms (561 samples at 44.1kHz). Window size and hop length were chosen to provide a detailed frequency-time representation of the snowmobile noises, enabling the model to discern unique spectral features. Finally, the spectrogram was split into 3 frequency bands: lower (0.00–7.35kHz), middle (7.35–14.70kHz) and upper (14.7–22.05kHz). Splitting the spectrogram into three frequency bands (lower, middle and upper) allowed the model to learn features across various frequency ranges, enhancing its capability to recognize snowmobile noises amidst a diverse array of sounds within different environments and conditions. The resulting spectrogram dimensions were [3, 341, 234].

Data augmentation is a practice which consists of artificially increasing the diversity of the dataset by slightly modifying the input data used to train the neural network. Data augmentation is especially useful when a low amount of training data is available (Salamon & Bello, 2017). To take advantage of our limited training dataset we made extensive use of data augmentation by using Python's audiomentations library (Jordal et al., 2022). In particular, we used time and frequency masking (i.e. this acts as a form of dropout of frequencies and time regions), we added time shifting, we applied a low pass-like filterbank with variable octave attenuation (i.e. to simulate the effect of distance), modified the frequency equalization (i.e. to simulate the change in the response characteristics of the microphone) and finally added Gaussian noise in the range [0.001, 0.015]. The probability for each of the augmentation types was set to 0.5.

Outdoor recordings are obtained in uncontrolled environments where extraneous noise signals are bound to contaminate the data. One particularly challenging type of contamination is wind noise, which includes both the acoustic sources that it creates (like the rustling of leaves) and pressure changes at the microphone's membrane that leave audible artefacts in the recording (Cook et al., 2021). Residual environmental noise such as wind and rain have been a major obstacle for bioacoustic detectors incorporating deep learning models thus far (though see Juodakis & Marsland, 2021; Metcalf et al., 2020) and failure to correctly account for weather noise can dramatically affect detector performance. Various approaches to environmental noise suppression have been developed for different tasks but classic denoising methods such as the Wiener or MMSE filters are not applicable to wind because of its rapid dynamics (Juodakis & Marsland, 2021).

The cyclic nature of a snowmobile's combustion engine (the fact that it operates at an approximately constant rpm given a short enough time segment), ensures that snowmobile engines produce a characteristic periodic signal, in clear contrast to the nonperiodic wind noise. Periodic signals (i.e. harmonic sounds) can be distinguished from nonperiodic signals (i.e. inharmonic sounds) with harmonicity descriptors. One such descriptor is the harmonic noise ratio (HNR; Moreau et al., 2006).

Therefore, we additionally computed the harmonic ratio for the lower frequencies (obtained by applying a low-pass butterworth filter) of the recordings. In our case, a lower HNR indicates that the source is nonperiodic, and is therefore more likely to contain wind instead of engine noise. Based on the results from the test dataset we classified a segment as containing snowmobile noise if the confidence of the snowmobile model was greater than or equal to 0.95, and the HNR larger than 0.1.

The pipeline for training the snowmobile detector was made in Python using PyTorch. The model was trained on a NVIDIA A40-24Q GPU.

2.3 | Analysis of the Yellowstone dataset

2.3.1 | Extracting snowmobile and bird detections

To be processed by the snowmobile model, each audio file is first split into non-overlapping 3s segments. Each audio chunk is then transformed into a spectrogram using a Fast Fourier transform window size of 46ms samples and a hop length of 13ms. Finally, the spectrogram passes through the snowmobile model, which outputs the model confidence of whether a snowmobile was present and the harmonic to noise ratio. In contrast, BirdNET accepts mel-spectrograms as input and each audio file is re-sampled to 48kHz, split into non-overlapping 3s segments and converted to a mel scale spectrogram of 64 bands that is passed through the model (Kahl et al., 2021).

It is possible to get a higher precision (i.e. lower rate of false positives) at the expense of a lower recall (i.e. higher rate of false negatives) by increasing the thresholds for both model confidence and harmonic ratio. For our analysis, we chose to lower the number of false positives by filtering for detections with high model confidence and high harmonic ratio. To select the model confidence and harmonic ratio threshold, we computed the F1 score for five increasing levels of filtering and chose the highest F1 score: (1) retaining the detections with harmonic ratio > 0.1, (2) retaining the detections with model confidence > 0.95 (MC 0.95+), (3) additionally retaining detections with HNR > 0.1 (MC 0.95+; HNR 0.1+), (4) additionally retaining detections with length ≥ 6s (MC 0.95+; HNR 0.1+; DL 6+) and (5) use model confidence > 0.99 while keeping HNR > 0.1 and duration ≥ 6s (MC 0.9+; HNR 0.1+; DL 6+; Figure 1-4).

We ran both our snowmobile detector model using the filtering that lead to the best F1-score (i.e. MC 0.9+; HNR 0.1+; DL

6+) and BirdNET Analyser V2.1 (Figure 1-5), on the Yellowstone dataset. BirdNET Analyser V2.1 was run with default parameters and a custom list of avian species found in Yellowstone (extracted from <https://irma.nps.gov/NPSpecies/Search/SpeciesList/YELL>, Supporting Document 1).

2.3.2 | Estimating trends in bird vocalization frequency with regards to snowmobile detections

To estimate the impact of detected snowmobiles on bird vocalizations, we first subsetted all detection data between 15 December and 15 March, the typical oversnow vehicle season at Yellowstone. To eliminate the possibility of false positive BirdNET detections triggered by a snowmobile event, any bird calls occurring during a snowmobile detection at the same site were removed from the analysis. We retained all BirdNET detections that did not occur during snowmobile events and assumed that any detection bias in the BirdNET model would be consistent prior to and after a snowmobile event. For each bird call, we identified the nearest snowmobile detection at that site before and after the call and extracted hourly wind speed, relative humidity and temperature from the Yellowstone Lake weather station (NOAA station P90, Herzmann, 2023, accessed via Iowa State University's Mesonet system; Figure 1-7). We aggregated the detections into buckets of 15s by summing the number of detections within each bucket (Figure 1-7). To reflect the phenology of bird vocalizations we added a variable time_of_day of value "AM" (i.e. morning), "MM" (i.e. afternoon) and "PM" (i.e. evening) if the 15s-bucket was located in the interval [6AM to 12PM], [12PM, 4PM] and [4PM, 12AM] respectively. Early morning hours [12AM to 6AM] were not analysed due to minimal bird vocalization activity and park restrictions on snowmobile use during these hours. We analysed only the four sites that contained the most detections (i.e. YELLOFWS, YELLMJ23, YELLFOPP and YELLGVLL; see Supplementary Map 1) as including sites with few detections would unnecessarily increase model uncertainty.

In the absence of concrete studies determining the precise distance at which birds can perceive engine noise, we opted to include bird vocalizations in the ranges [240, 0] and [0, 240s] (Figure 2) before and after the detection of a snowmobile resulting in a dataset containing 34,941 individual bird calls. This decision is based on extrapolations from human auditory capabilities.

In ideal conditions such as the relatively quiet environment of Yellowstone National Park, low wind speed and assuming a sufficiently loud snowmobile, research suggests that a human could potentially detect the sound from approximately 2km away (engine noise can become a nuisance or safety concern at 400–800m, suggesting that it is audible at least this far way, Franks et al., 1996; Miedema & Oudshoorn, 2001). Taking into account a snowmobile travelling at an average speed of 8.33m/s (i.e. 30km/h), this translates to humans possibly beginning to hear the snowmobile around 4min (i.e. 2000m/8.33m/s=240s) before it passes their location. Given the uncertainty surrounding the distance at which a bird can

FIGURE 2 Example of a spectrogram showing the obtention of the distance from bird vocalization (orange square, obtained by BirdNET) to the snowmobile detection (light blue square). The distance from the bird vocalization before and after (green arrow) the snowmobile detection (light blue square) is computed from the start and end of the snowmobile detection.

hear a snowmobile, we also tested how different ranges influenced our results in a sensitivity analysis (see the Supplementary [Method, Results and Discussion](#) in the Supplementary Material).

We used linear models ([Figure 1-8](#)) with the log of the number of bird calls (i.e. the number of calls in the 15 s bucket) as the response variable (Gaussian error distribution) and the interaction between the time before or after detection of a snowmobile and time of day. The variable representing time before or after detection of a snowmobile has been log-transformed to better represent acoustic properties, in particular the inverse square law which states that for each doubling of distance from a source point, the sound pressure level decreases by approximately 6 dB. Moreover, log-transformation implies that the effect is null at infinite distance, that is if the snowmobile is not heard then its effect on the avifauna is null. We chose a Gaussian model over a Poisson model (typical for count data such as ours) because the later model showed a high degree of overdispersion. Log-transforming our response variable solved the problem. To control for the effect of environmental variables on the log-transformed number of bird calls, we included the following variables: hourly wind speed, relative humidity and temperature as explanatory variables. To account for the dependency of observations from the same site and from the same day, we included 'site' and 'date' as crossed random effects. The nearest hourly weather reading was related to each snowmobile and each individual bird call detection. Any gaps in available weather data were filled using linear interpolation. Sites and dates were included as random effects. All numerical variables were z-score normalized.

The models were fitted using the glmmTMB package (Magnusson et al., 2017) in R 4.2.2 (R Core Team, 2022) and we assessed the fit of the model using the DHARMA package (Hartig & Hartig, 2017).

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Snowmobile detection model performance

Columns of the matrices represent an increasing level of filtering. MC 0.95+ and 0.99+ corresponds to retaining all detections with model confidence >0.95 or 0.99 respectively; HNR 0.1+ corresponds to retaining all detections with HNR >0.1; DL 6+ corresponds to

retaining all detections which are at least 6 s long. The filtering parameters used on the entire Yellowstone dataset are displayed in the last column (MC 0.99+, HNR 0.1+ and DL 6+).

Our results show that accounting for wind using a filter on the harmonic ratio value greatly increases model performance ([Figure 3](#)). When detections are only filtered using the snowmobile model confidence (>0.95) we obtain a precision of 0.11 (i.e. on average, among 100 positive identifications only 11 are really snowmobiles). When detections are filtered using the harmonic ratio only, we obtain a precision of 0.12. However, when filtering detections based on both model confidence (>0.95) and harmonic ratio (>0.100), the precision reaches 0.5, suggesting both methods are complementary. For both MC 0.95+ and MC 0.95+ HNR 0.1+, the recall is of 0.98 (i.e. on average, the model correctly detects 98% of all snowmobiles). Accounting for detection length (detections that are at least 6 s long) in addition to model confidence and HNR further increases the precision while slightly decreasing the recall (precision=0.65; recall=0.94). The final set of parameters filtered by model confidence >0.99 and yielded an increased precision (0.78) while reducing the recall (0.77), displaying the tradeoff between these metrics.

3.2 | Effect of snowmobile detection on number of bird vocalizations

Histograms of the average number of bird vocalizations across sites for the three different times of day displayed in [Figure 4](#) suggest a decrease of the number of bird vocalizations before the detection of a snowmobile in the morning and in the evening (average number of vocalizations in morning=1.55, 1.58, 1.35; average number of vocalizations in evening=1.44, 1.39, 1.26 in the ranges [240s, 225s], [135s, 120s] and [15s, 0s]) and an increase after detection of the snowmobile for morning, afternoon and evening (average number of vocalizations in morning=1.34, 1.49, 1.55; average number of vocalizations in afternoon=1.31, 1.50, 1.50 and average number of vocalizations in evening=1.32, 1.43, 1.39 in the ranges [0s, 15s], [120s, 135s] and [225s, 240s]).

The statistical models confirm that the passage of snowmobile significantly influence the number of bird vocalizations as there is

FIGURE 3 Confusion matrix (a) for snowmobile event detection on the test dataset after different levels of filtering and (b) figure displaying the model performance metrics by filtering type.

FIGURE 4 Histograms of the number of bird calls and predicted number of bird calls in 15 s intervals before (a) and after (b) detection of a snowmobile, averaged across all the sites in the Yellowstone dataset. The average number of bird vocalizations predicted by our model is displayed by the line. The 95% confidence interval is also displayed. The p -values represent the significance level for the interaction between time of day (t -test with 95% confidence interval).

a significant decrease of the number bird vocalizations before detection of a snowmobile in the morning and evening (i.e. p -values for the estimated marginal means for the interaction between time of day and before detection of a snowmobile <0.0001 for both morning and evening, Figure 3 and Table S1) and a significant increase of the

number of bird vocalizations after the detection of a snowmobile in the morning and in the afternoon (i.e. p -values for the estimated marginal means for the interaction between time of day and after detection of a snowmobile <0.0001 , <0.0001 for morning and afternoon, Figure 3 and Table S1).

Model predictions indicate that the predicted number of bird vocalizations 240 and 0s before detection of a snowmobile lead to a decrease of 0.26 vocalizations (1.47–1.12 vocalizations per 15 s bin) and 0.24 (1.34 to 1.10 vocalizations) translating to the loss of 24% and 18% of the predicted number of vocalizations in the morning and evening, respectively. The predicted number of vocalizations however remains stable in the afternoon 240 and 0s before the detection of a snowmobile. In contrast, the model predicts that the number of bird vocalizations 0 and 240s after detection of a snowmobile increases by an average of 0.28 (from 1.15 to 1.43), 0.29 (from 1.08 to 1.37) and 0.15 (from 1.17 to 1.32) vocalizations for morning, afternoon and evening. This translates into a gain of 24%, 26% and 13% of vocalizations.

4 | DISCUSSION

In this study, we used a combination of deep learning and statistical techniques to assess the impact of snowmobile noise on bird vocalizations. Our findings provide valuable insights into the relationships between snowmobile noise and avian vocalization patterns during the non-breeding winter season. The automated snowmobile detection model we developed proved effective in identifying snowmobile noise in the acoustic monitoring data collected in Yellowstone National Park. By applying this model to a large winter acoustic dataset, we were able to analyse the temporal effects of snowmobile noise on bird vocalizations.

Our findings revealed that snowmobile noise had a significant effect on avian vocalizations during the non-breeding winter season, which has been an understudied area in the literature. The passage of snowmobiles led to a decrease in the frequency of bird vocalizations both during mornings and evenings, indicating a disturbance to their communication. Nevertheless, we observe an increase in the frequency of bird vocalization after the detection of a snowmobile, indicating a recovery in avian vocalization and potentially indicating some resilience to the effect of sporadic noise events such as passage of snowmobiles.

Increased noise levels have been shown to have implications for breeding success and habitat selection in birds (Kight & Swaddle, 2011; Ware et al., 2015), but much less is known about noise impacts on wintering birds. Understanding these effects in the non-breeding season is crucial for a comprehensive assessment of the impacts of noise on avian communities throughout their life cycle. Many wintering birds exhibit flocking behaviour to improve foraging success and avoid predators (Davies et al., 2012), and within-flock calls help birds avoid predators, find food, and coordinate movements (Freeberg & Lucas, 2002). Noise disturbances to flock communication may thus disrupt important winter behaviours like foraging, predator avoidance and pre-breeding season mate selection. Disturbances to winter flock communication may thus have indirect impacts on breeding season outcomes: breeding pairs often form between birds who are members of the same winter flocks (Firth et al., 2018; Psorakis et al., 2012; Saitou, 1979), and these

partnerships can improve breeding success in wild passerine populations (Culina et al., 2020). Though we discovered a statistically significant impact of snowmobile noise on avian vocalization detections, it is unclear whether the observed short-term effect size would constitute a substantial long-term biological impact on distribution and abundance. It was outside the scope of this study to assess other potential impacts of noise on wintering birds, such as avoidance altogether of noisy corridors. However, research suggests that winter avian abundance and distribution is driven more by food availability than by road or rail noise (Wiącek et al., 2019; Wiącek & Polak, 2015), so if food availability happens to be high near a snowmobile corridor, it is possible that wintering birds will risk the potential impacts of snowmobile noise to their communication.

The results of this study underscore the importance of considering noise impacts in the broader context of habitat loss and climate change, as anthropogenic noise can act as a significant stressor, potentially synergistically with other stressors on wildlife populations (Francis et al., 2009). By quantifying the extent of the influence of snowmobile engine noise on avian vocalizations in the non-breeding season, our research contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the stressors facing avian communities.

This case study may provide insights for natural resource managers who balance snowmobile recreation and avian conservation priorities. The effect size observed in the study is small but statistically significant; results must be contextualized within circumstances of the Yellowstone dataset. In the middle of the acoustic monitoring period covered by this study, Yellowstone National Park adopted a Winter Use Plan (National Park Service, 2013), which included restrictions on the total number of daily oversnow vehicle transportation events allowed in the park, a list of allowable “best available technology” snowmobiles, a 67 dBA limit on snowmobiles operated within the park, and an Adaptive Management Program to assess whether oversnow vehicle use is exceeding the predicted noise budget. Existing management practices, such as event grouping and use of best available technologies, thus may have mitigated the impacts found in this study. Impacts of noise on winter bird vocalizations might be larger in locations with no noise mitigation measures in place. In such areas, managers might choose to minimize disturbance and protect critical habitat areas. For example, implementing speed restrictions or designated snowmobile-free zones in areas with high avian activity during specific hours in the winter season (e.g. morning) may reduce disturbance to bird vocalization activity.

It should be noted that the time window used in this analysis (i.e. [240s, 0s], [0s, 240s] before and after detection of a snowmobile, respectively) has been chosen based on extrapolations from human auditory capabilities. We acknowledge the differences in hearing capacities and perception between humans and birds (Dooling, 2002), as well as the wide range of variables that can influence such estimates (e.g. wind, landscape profile). However, lacking more specific data, we believe we offer a reasonable starting point for analysing the impact of snowmobile noise on bird communities. Results from the sensitivity analysis (see the Supplementary [Method, Results and Discussion](#)) indicate that selecting shorter time window increase the

negative effect snowmobile has on the number of bird vocalizations. When the temporal scope is narrowed, the impact of specific ecological, environmental and behavioural elements on bird vocalization frequencies might become less pronounced and the effect of snowmobile noise becomes predominant.

The methodology we developed for assessing noise impacts from snowmobiles using deep learning techniques offers significant advantages for both scientific research and management purposes. By automating the detection and classification of snowmobile noise, we were able to analyse large amounts of acoustic monitoring data efficiently and accurately. This automated approach not only saves time and effort compared to manual sound annotation but also allows for the examination of a larger temporal and geographic scope, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of snowmobile noise on avian vocalizations. Nevertheless, the bird classifier model we used (i.e. BirdNET) is unable to identify the type of call emitted and it is not possible to differentiate between alarm, call or song. Such analysis would require custom built deep learning models trained on the specific calls of each bird species. We have not investigated the effect of snowmobile noise on particular species either as we aggregated the number of calls independently of the species. This is due to the lack of documentation on BirdNET's performance on particular species and results of such analysis could be misleading. While it is possible to obtain BirdNET's precision and accuracy for different species (Sethi et al., 2021), it is resource consuming and can hardly be scaled for large numbers of bird species.

While our study is restricted to the immediate vocal responses of the avifauna, it does not delve into analysing longer-term behavioural effects, such as avoidance behaviours or alterations in feeding and mating patterns, which may also be consequential in understanding the holistic impact of noise pollution on avian populations. However, the paradigm and methodology employed herein, which amalgamate passive acoustic monitoring and deep learning techniques, harbour the potential to be extrapolated for investigating longer-term effects of noise on bird populations, spanning hours to days, thereby providing a versatile framework that could be instrumental in future research exploring the prolonged impacts of noise on avian behaviours and ecology.

In conclusion, our study demonstrates a small impact of snowmobile noise on avian vocalizations during the non-breeding winter season in the Yellowstone National Park. The application of deep learning techniques allowed for efficient detection and analysis of snowmobile noise, providing valuable insights into the relationships between anthropogenic noise and avian vocalization patterns. This research has important implications for the management of natural areas where recreation and wildlife conservation coexist, highlighting the need for measures to mitigate noise impacts on avian communities and protect critical habitats.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Benjamin Cretois, Femke B. Gelderblom and Tor Arne Reinen developed the snowmobile detection model. Julia Wiel labelled the training and test dataset. Benjamin Cretois, Diego Pávon-Jordán and

Ian Avery Bick analysed the detections resulting from the snowmobile and BirdNET models. The Yellowstone dataset was provided by Cathleen Balantic, Davyd H. Betchkal and Ben Banet. The manuscript was drafted by Benjamin Cretois and Ian Avery Bick. Carolyn M. Rosten and Sarab S. Sethi provided comments in the early state of the manuscript and actively contributed to the manuscript writing. All authors provided feedback and approved the manuscript.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Code for running the snowmobile model is available on GitHub (https://github.com/NINAnor/snowmobile_analyzer). The repository also contains the R scripts and dataset used to run the statistical modelling. The data are also available from Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10259296> (Cretois et al., 2023).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Supplementary Map 1. Map of the sites analyzed by both the snowmobile and bird classification model.

Supplementary Method, Results and Discussion. Description and results of the sensitivity analysis.

Table S1. Estimated marginal means and contrasts for the interaction between time of day and snowmobile detection. *p*-values have been determined using *t*-tests (95% confidence interval).

Table S2. Results from the linear models. In bold text are the significant coefficients (*p*-value < 0.05).

Supporting Document 1. Table listing the species list used as input to BirdNET.

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Paper 3:

National-scale acoustic monitoring of avian biodiversity and migration

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Contribution Statement:

Led acoustic recorder site selection process. Contributed to the installation and recovery of recorders in the field. Performed all analyses and led writing of the manuscript.

National-scale acoustic monitoring of avian biodiversity and migration

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Abstract

Billions of birds migrate annually, triggered by endogenous behaviors as well as ecoclimatic triggers, which are shifting with climate change. These dynamics play out over large spatiotemporal scales, making monitoring of phenology challenging with traditional biodiversity survey approaches. In this study, over a complete spring season, we collected 37,429 hours of audio from 28 networked sensors in forests across Norway. We used machine learning to automatically identify bird vocalizations, and with expert validation found we were able to classify 57 species (14 full migrants) with over 80% precision. We show that acoustic surveys can fill data gaps in traditional surveys and facilitate mapping of migratory waves across Norwegian forests. Our study demonstrates how acoustic monitoring can complement existing national-scale biodiversity datasets, delivering high quality data which can support the design and implementation of effective policy and conservation measures.

Main

Around the world, climate change, habitat loss, and pollution are having severe impacts on biodiversity (1), an integral aspect to each of the 17 United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (2). Monitoring biodiversity and species' responses to stressors and interventions is critical for informing and evaluating conservation and land management strategies (3, 4). Traditionally, ecologists rely on citizen science to track avian phenology, populations, and inform conservation policy (5) through either national breeding bird surveys or apps such as eBird, iNaturalist, and Artsobservasjoner.

Breeding bird surveys are typically performed by knowledgeable volunteers (6) and capture a snapshot of bird populations in the late-Spring and early-Summer across thousands of sites in the northern hemisphere (6). While these surveys are a thorough and crucial means of estimating population trends and ranges for many species (5), their lack of temporal resolution makes them ineffective for studying migratory timing and phenology, such as shifts in Spring migratory bird arrival timing with global warming (1, 3). Conversely, datasets which allow the public to record observations opportunistically (e.g., eBird) provide some insight into avian phenology timing (7) but suffer from temporal and spatial biases (8) and a high variation in data reliability (9). Ecologists have also long employed weather radars to track birds and migratory patterns over large distances (10). While radar methods effectively track aggregate migrant behavior, such as identifying stopover locations (10), they cannot easily distinguish between species.

Automated approaches are increasingly being used to complement manual surveys by improving the scale and resolution of biodiversity monitoring (11). Passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) has shown particular promise due to the approach's taxonomic breadth (12) and scalability for both data analysis and collection (11). Automated analysis of audio is becoming commonplace, supported by the growth of powerful machine learning (ML) models (13). ML algorithms such as BirdNET can accurately identify hundreds of species from recordings and anthropogenic noise pollution (14, 15), while others are used to detect biodiversity pressures such as noise pollution (16), illegal logging (17), or poaching (18, 19). Autonomous and real-time acoustic data collection via cellular network connection and self-powered units (via solar power or connection to a grid) is also growing (20, 21), but few studies (22) have put data collection and analysis together to deliver biodiversity insight at scales and resolutions that would not be possible with traditional methods.

The study of avian species phenology is particularly well-suited for PAM. Many birds are highly vocal, and their dynamics and distributions extend over scales and resolutions that are not easily captured by traditional surveys. Furthermore, due to large existing vocalization libraries, off-the-shelf bird vocalization detection ML models cover thousands of species and are increasingly reliable (14, 15, 22). Improved monitoring of avian phenology could help us understand how stressors such as noise pollution (23), habitat loss (24), and climate change (e.g., "spring mismatch" (3, 25)) impact avian migration routes, behaviors, and breeding outcomes at relevant scales, informing conservation policy in an era of rapid ecological change (26).

In this study, we perform one of the first national-scale acoustic surveys (27) of avian phenology using autonomous acoustic recorders installed across almost the entire latitudinal extent of Norway. We

demonstrate that PAM can measure avian phenology at high resolution across large scales, that detections of vocalizations from an ML model are reliable for many species through expert validation, and that PAM provides complementary biodiversity data to existing surveys. We also show that by relating PAM detections to ecoclimatic variables (28), it is possible to visualize the spread of avian vocalization probability across Spring migration at a national scale.

PAM is reliable and fills data gaps in existing surveys

Our solar-powered, networked PAM stations were installed from Kristiansand on the southern tip of Norway, to Finnmark in the far north, approximately 1,700 km apart (Fig. 1a). Between April 1 and June 30, 2022, we collected 37,429 hours of audio data from 28 sites in eight regional clusters, with an average 75% recorder uptime. Having redundant recorders in each region provided pseudo-replicate data and covered for periods of power loss or recorder failure (see sites Bergen 3 and Kristiansand 1 in Fig. 1b,c). Recordings were saved locally in 5-minute files, then uploaded to a cloud server via mobile internet, where BirdNET was used to detect and classify bird vocalizations.

We utilized an expert validation methodology to understand the precision of BirdNET classifications in our study area and focus our analysis on species that the model detections with high precision. Fifty BirdNET detections, and their corresponding audio, were provided to an expert ornithologist for 67 species which had at least 50 BirdNET detections with a model confidence (29) over 0.80. After expert labeling of these recordings, we find that BirdNET correctly identified 57 species (including 14 full migrants) with greater than 80% precision and 30 of these with 100% precision (Fig. 1d). From the vocalizations of the 14 reliably detectable migrant species, we were able to observe increasing species richness through the spring months as well as latitudinal differences in biodiversity and migratory arrival (Fig. 1c)

surveys for WW across the study period within our study regions ($N_{\text{PAM}} = 687$, $N_{\text{eBird}} = 102$, $N_{\text{BBS}} = 135$), CC ($N_{\text{PAM}} = 300$, $N_{\text{eBird}} = 48$, $N_{\text{BBS}} = 63$), and SF ($N_{\text{PAM}} = 192$, $N_{\text{eBird}} = 60$, $N_{\text{BBS}} = 45$), primarily driven by the large number of days when acoustic data was recorded but no eBird or BBS survey were performed (light blue, Fig. 2). We note a distinct two-peak pattern of vocalization frequency over time for the three species (Fig. 2a,d,e), that has previously been observed for Willow Warbler (32) and other passerines (33). The first peak in mid-May represents the pre-breeding season (Fig. 2a), with males establishing territory and performing courtship (32). This is followed by a drop in vocalization during pairing, then a second increase during laying and incubation, which may be due to males performing song to attract second females (32).

As BBS is only performed between late May to early July, we also compared detections solely on days where both BBS and PAM data were available. BBS (red, Fig. 2c, 2f, 2i) generally had a higher probability of uniquely detecting these species than PAM (dark blue, Fig. 2c, 2f, 2i), with 42 unique daily detections across the three species compared to 13 for PAM. Similarly, eBird also exhibited a higher detection sensitivity than PAM on days where both surveys were conducted, with 21 to 14 unique daily detections, respectively (Fig. 2b, 2e, 2h). With only two to five recorders per 90 km x 90 km region, PAM provides greater sampling effort temporally, giving phenological context for manual surveys which are concentrated during breeding season. In contrast, BBS had a greater spatial sampling effort, being much more likely to have a unique daily detection of these three species than PAM.

Fig. 2 | For three common migrating passerines, passive acoustic monitoring data can fill gaps and improve temporal resolution of sampling compared to existing biodiversity datasets, but on days where manual surveys and PAM were conducted, manual surveys had more unique detections. a, d, g, Audio recorders in Bergen capture temporal patterns in species arrival and vocalization for three migrating passerine species (green bars). Detections (green lines) and non-detections (red lines) from manual surveys in this region fail to capture avian migratory dynamics at the same resolution. PAM captures more total detections of species of interest than b,e,h, eBird and c,f,i, BBS. However, on days where both audio surveys and manual surveys were performed, both eBird and BBS were more sensitive for detecting each species.

PAM enables avian phenology monitoring at a national scale

In Bergen, we estimated that CC, WW, and SF arrived on April 23, May 4, and May 27, respectively (Fig. 3d, Methods). This order of establishment agrees with intuition based on CC wintering further north than WW and SF, which are long-distance migrants, and thus arriving sooner. The timings also align with these species' respective food sources: primarily crawling insects and larvae for WW and CC, but flying insects for SF, which emerge later in the Spring season. Based on arrival times in Kristiansand and Tromsø, WW traveled northward at approximately 67 km/day, agreeing with previous measurements of WW southward autumn migratory rate of 40.6-80.5 km/day using ringed birds (34). Intuitively, we found that at higher latitudes WW arrives at a lower greenness, as measured by satellite-derived Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) (35) (Spearman $\rho = -0.83$, $p = 0.04$). As migrating birds must contend with short breeding seasons in northern regions, they often carefully balance their arrival times to match

the timing snowmelt and greening of northern birch forests (36), ideally matching peak food abundance to when chicks are present in their nests (37). Mistiming migration to these colder, northern areas may lead to mortality (37, 38) and climatic changes in wintering areas in Africa seem to have driven WW to arrive approximately half a day earlier to the Tromsø region each year since 1995 (37), potentially threatening this phenological timing. Whilst previously only investigated at regional scales (26), our results show that large PAM networks have the potential to reveal long-term changes in avian migratory phenology on national scales and beyond, identifying species or ecosystems at the most risk from climate change.

Fig. 3 | Cumulative audio detections of migrating passerines demonstrate interspecies and large-scale variation in migration timing across Norway. a, b, c, d, Passive acoustic monitoring shows ecologically consistent species arrival patterns across Norway (30). Spotted Flycatcher, with a diet of flying insects, arrives later than both Willow Warbler and Common Chiffchaff, whose diets include primarily larvae and crawling insects. **e,** Willow Warbler arriving at higher latitudes arrive at a much lower greenness index than those at lower latitudes (Spearman $\rho=-0.83$, $p=0.04$), illustrating a potential tradeoff between lower competition in northern regions, but also lower food availability.

We next hyperparameter-tuned and trained random forest regression models (39) to act as acoustic species distribution models (aSDMs) (28) by predicting the weekly probability of hearing WW and SF vocalizations based on several ecoclimatic features. The aSDMs allowed us to extrapolate spatially beyond our sampling sites to other forested regions (40) similar to where we've sampled, mapping migratory waves of birds based on their probability of vocalization (Fig. 4) at a resolution of 0.2 degrees,

approximately 10 km. With the national-scale aSDMs, we observed WW's earlier arrival and higher relative abundance than SF across Norway, as demonstrated by their vocalization probabilities (Fig. 4a,b). Between May 8-14, the model predicts that Willow Warbler are largely not yet vocalizing in the northern Tromsø region, but that these areas are populated two weeks later. This aligns with both the raw species detections (Fig. 3b) and the estimate of May 14 as the first arrival date of Willow Warbler in Troms County by Barrett (2002) (36).

To test the agreement of the aSDMs with eBird and BBS survey data in forested regions, we sampled the distributions of aSDM values at survey observation points, observing whether higher aSDM vocalization probabilities were associated with positive observations from manual surveys (Fig. 4c,d). The aSDMs agree well with eBird observations by permutation test (Fig. 4c,d) of WW ($p \leq 0.001$, $t = 0.102$) and SF ($p = 0.014$, $t = 0.071$). Similarly, Bota et al 2020 found that avian vocal activity rate of European Bee-eaters, as detected by PAM recorders, correlated positively with their inclusion in complete checklists from citizen scientists (41). However, we see that the aSDMs for WW do not significantly agree with the BBS observations (Fig. 4d), perhaps due to the limited temporal range of BBS in late May and June, during which WW are nearly ubiquitous across Norwegian forests (Fig. 4a). In contrast, the BBS observations agree with the aSDM for SF, which have a more heterogenous distribution (Fig. 4b). The general agreement of the aSDMs with citizen-science based datasets illustrates the complementary nature of PAM with survey data. As the aSDM vocalization probabilities capture a metric of species detectability (9, 42), they also offer a means of informing the timing of both breeding bird surveys and more casual citizen scientists. Such aSDM models may also be extended to project how conditions suitable for species vocalization may change over time with climate change (28).

Fig. 4 | Combining audio vocalization detections with ecoclimatic variables allowed us to train audio species distribution models (aSDMs) to predict vocalization probability as an analogue of species occurrence across Norway. Weekly vocalization probability in forested areas across Norway (30) for **a**, Willow Warbler and **b**, Spotted Flycatcher shows spatiotemporal species arrival patterns and captures later arrival of Spotted Flycatcher relative to Willow Warbler. **c**, At eBird survey points, the distribution of aSDM values are significantly greater when the surveyor detected WW and SF versus when the eBird surveyor did not detect the species. **d**, For BBS survey points, the distribution of aSDM values is significantly greater when the surveyor detected SF, but not for WW.

Discussion and Future Work

Our results show that national-scale PAM deployments can deliver a step change in both the resolution and scale at which we can track avian phenology when compared to existing manual surveys. Pairing networked sensors and automated analyses with one-off expert validation allowed us to track phenology reliably and in near real-time and required minimal cost and effort to deploy and maintain. However, even with improved temporal resolution and lower labor requirements, PAM methods should be viewed as a complement to existing manual observation methods, such as breeding bird surveys. For instance, PAM cannot easily distinguish between vocalizations of resident birds in an area versus those who are passing migrant individuals, or discern whether calls are from individual birds or multiple, without the use of multiple microphones in a single array (43). Breeding bird surveys are designed specifically to count

breeding pairs during the period after most migrants have arrived, typically June in Norway. Therefore, PAM observations before this period represent occurrence of a migrating species, but not necessarily their population or residency within a given area.

The expert validation approach employed here enabled estimation of BirdNET model precision in identifying bird vocalizations but is limited by inability to calculate recall. Calculating recall would involve calculating the fraction of actual vocalizations that are correctly detected by BirdNET, requiring each detection to be manually checked for all species. This would be a challenge considering there were 33,643 detections with a model confidence over 0.80. We argue that precision provides a more useful metric, critical for ensuring reliable detections in remote areas with lower bird populations and for facilitating stakeholder trust in model results. However, by thresholding detections at a model confidence over 0.80 for validation, we subsequently filtered out 81% of the total detections from our recorders, possibly significantly reducing the model's recall at the expense of our higher precision (44). Depending on goals, future studies may consider lowering thresholds for model confidence, or setting model confidence thresholds on a species-by-species basis (14). Financial and practical limitations also affected the number of recorders deployed to each region, making our study sensitive to failure of some recording devices (see Fig. 1) and introducing possible spatial bias in the total number of detections by region, though we partially corrected for this by normalizing daily detections by the daily number of hours recorded.

Future studies may take advantage of the fact that sensors are becoming cheaper, more sensitive, and more reliable (18) while machine learning models for identifying species by vocalization are improving in accuracy, taxonomic breadth (e.g., insects, mammals), and computational efficiency (13), making national-scale PAM surveys more readily implementable. Efforts to provide large-scale, comprehensive biodiversity mapping, such as the Dutch ARISE program (45), may eventually draw upon multiple sources of species observations, including PAM, camera traps (46), drones (47), citizen science (48), and formal surveys (6). Ultimately, PAM has the potential to transform our understanding of species phenology and can pave the way for effective data-driven conservation and policy decision making, leading to improved outcomes for biodiversity globally.

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Materials and Methods

Recording Site Selection

Recording sites were located at BBS survey points (within 100m) to maximize compatibility between the two datasets. The sites were also restricted to forested areas, as determined by the “Forest” IPCC Class in 300m resolution land cover data from Copernicus (40). When possible, sites were chosen within 200m of accessible roads (49) or trails for ease of deployment and within areas with 4G data coverage. To maintain confidentiality of BBS survey points, random noise of up to 1 km was added to the location of each recorder in the publicly available version of this dataset.

Across Spring 2022 in Norway, 28 recording stations were installed across eight regions (from south to north): Kristiansand (5), Stavanger (2), Moss (3), Bergen (3), Lillehammer (2), Trondheim (4), Tromsø (4), and Finnmark (5). The different numbers of recorders per region were due to physical and logistical difficulties installing records in certain locations, including land access or unavailable sunlight. While uncorrected spatial biases could exist in our analyses, we do correct for total number of hours recorded per region to partially alleviate this, as described below in the description of methods for estimating species arrival.

These recorders were then grouped into regions, defined by a 90 x 90 km box sharing a centroid with the recorders, the largest size possible without overlap between regions. The Finnmark cluster of recorders was dropped from species arrival analysis, as only one valid detection of a species of interest for this study was found. However, these sites are included in Figure 1 and for training and evaluating the audio

species distribution models (Fig. 4). Sites within clusters were spread such that each could be considered acoustically independent (i.e., >100m apart, see Sethi et al 2020(50)).

Audio Collection

In total, 73,516 hours of audio was collected from March to October 2022. Audio at each site was collected using a Bugg device 1-2m from ground level. Devices were powered through using 50-100W solar panels and 20-30 Ah 12V batteries, and thus were sensitive to shade and cloud cover. Still, 19 of 28 recorders had uptimes over 75% across the study period. The Bugg recorders used a built-in Knowles SPH0641LU4H-1 omnidirectional PDM MEMS microphone, with a 100Hz-80KHz dynamic range, which was weatherproofed using an acoustic ePTFE membrane (51).

Files were saved locally in five-minute increments at a 44.1 kHz sampling rate in compressed MP3 format (VBR0 using FFMPEG's LAME codec), then uploaded to a Google Cloud server via the 4G network. Previous work has found MP3 compression at such high quality has little effect on downstream eco-acoustic analyses (52). Where network service was unavailable, audio data was manually uploaded upon device retrieval in Fall 2022.

Species Detection

Audio data was processed on a custom Google Cloud web app using BirdNET-lite (53) to extract and identify vocalizations to species level in near real-time (15). In total, 176 unique species were identified in this dataset by BirdNET-lite. Of these, 67 species had at least 50 detections with a model confidence over 0.8. For this subset, we provided an expert ornithologist with 50 random detections for each species, sampled across all sites without stratification, with each species taking approximately 20-30 minutes to validate. Of these, BirdNET-lite correctly identified 57 species with 80% or greater precision. Of these species, 14 are full migrants to Norway each Spring and were considered when calculating daily avian species richness at each site.

Species Arrival

We calculated species arrival for a subset of three fully migrant passerines that were commonly detected in our dataset and had high detection accuracy from BirdNET: Willow Warbler (*Phylloscopus trochilus*), Spotted Flycatcher (*Muscicapa striata*), and Common Chiffchaff (*Phylloscopus collybita*). We defined the study period as April 1 through June 30, 2022, by which most migrating bird species have arrived across Norway. In the Northern regions of Finnmark and Tromsø, recorders were installed in early May.

With snow still covering the area, this temporal discrepancy is unlikely to miss observations—the first Willow Warbler in Tromsø was detected in mid-May, agreeing with previous manual estimates of first arrival (36).

We estimated the date of migratory arrival for each species at a given region by setting a threshold of 5% total detections across our study period, a common method for setting arrival dates in migratory studies (54). Thus, when calculating arrival for a given species, we only consider regions with more than 20 valid detections. To correct for varying spatiotemporal sampling effort, the daily detections of each species were normalized by the daily sum of recorder uptime within each region. To calculate the percentage of total vocalizations over time, we first take a cumulative sum of these normalized uptimes across the study period, then normalized these from 0 to 1. We estimate the date of species arrival as the first day with $\geq 5\%$ of total vocalizations. We then plot arrival curves along with normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), sourced from the daily 0.05 degree resolution gap-filled MODIS Vegetation Index dataset (35). Daily NDVI per region is calculated by averaging all NDVI cells within each 90x90 km region.

Comparison of Audio to Manual Survey Methods

eBird and BBS Surveys

Raw eBird surveys (31) were aggregated within each 90x90 km region, then filtered by several criteria to standardize data (9). First, to ensure that pseudo-absences could be assumed from eBird surveys, only complete checklists were included, those where observers marked that all observed species were included. Surveys with high effort—those traveling over 5km or lasting longer than 90 minutes—were dropped to ensure that observations occurred close to the provided survey start coordinates (9). Duplicate surveys that appear in group surveys were dropped. Lastly, surveys in non-forested areas, as identified by the Copernicus data set (40), were dropped to ensure comparability against the audio dataset. Lastly, surveys were filtered to the elevation range of our recording stations, 73m to 764m.

Typically, Norwegian Breeding Bird Survey (BBS) data is spatially aggregated to protect the specific coordinates of survey points from increased traffic which could affect avian nesting habits. Non-public BBS data was obtained from the survey organizers (6) for the three migrating passerines of interest. The dataset consists of observations of the number of breeding pairs of each species at 9,257 unique points across Norway by experienced volunteers. Many volunteers are trained by attending the BIRD ID course at Nord University, but a prerequisite for all is good knowledge of bird sounds and appearance. Regional coordinators communicate with observers before they perform surveys, and observations are skipped in rare cases where poor knowledge or reduced hearing abilities is suspected by the survey organizers. The

BBS is carried out from 20 May through 10 July each year after all species have arrived at their breeding sites, to be able to exclude individuals that are traveling. Volunteers travel along transects, making observations at several points. Between 4AM and 10AM, they count the number of breeding pairs they observe in 5 minutes at each point, visiting each point only once (6). These observations were also filtered to forested regions and to the elevation range (73m to 764m) of our recording stations.

Audio Species Distribution Models

We trained and cross-validated a random forest regression model on several weekly ecoclimatic covariates (55) to predict the probability of vocalization (28) for Willow Warbler and Spotted Flycatcher. The weekly binary detection (0,1) of a species at each of the 28 sites served as the target variable, with weekly averages of NDVI (35), maximum (56), minimum (57), and mean (58) temperature, and precipitation (59), as well as site elevation (60) as the predictor variables. Predictor variables were extracted for each site's coordinates. In Finnmark and Tromsø, where snow cover continues late into the spring, several weeks of NDVI coverage were not available from the MODIS dataset (35) and were zero-filled. The random forest regression models were hyperparameter-tuned using a random grid search approach over 1,000 iterations. The model parameters with the best mean squared error performance on the test set were chosen via 4-fold cross-validation. The tuned model parameters and train and test set errors are available in SI Table 2.

We then generated weekly aSDMs using the trained models for each species. Covariate rasters were resampled to a common resolution of 0.2 degrees (epsg:4326) (approximately 10 km) and used to predict probability of vocalization across Norway. To restrict our vocalization probability maps to ecosystems similar to our study sites, we employ a masking step to filter out non-majority-forested cells from the aSDM based on the 300m resolution Copernicus land cover dataset (40). Lastly, aSDMs were then compared against the filtered complete eBird and BBS lists (i.e., presence and absence included). For each month, we compared the distributions of aSDM values with positive survey detections (1) and for the survey absences (0) using a permutation test with 1,000 resamples and alternative “greater”. This test evaluates whether the means of the distributions of aSDM values were greater when eBird or BBS detects a species, versus when they do not.

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Author Contributions

CR, SSS, and BC organized the Sound of Norway (thesoundofnorway.com) project which facilitated this study. IAB identified suitable locations for acoustic recorders and worked with CR to receive landowner permissions to deploy recorders. CR, SSS, IAB, and JW deployed and collected acoustic recorders. IAB, SSS, MS, and BH developed methodologies and research objectives, with advisement from VB, MP, and KR. IAB performed all data processing and modeling and generated all figures. IAB drafted the manuscript with significant contributions from SSS. All coauthors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Data Availability

All code, manual survey data, acoustic detections, and ecoclimatic covariates required to generate each figure in this study are available at doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11238950. Random noise of up to 0.01 degrees has been added to all coordinates of recording stations and Norwegian Breeding Bird survey points to maintain the confidentiality and data integrity of the survey.

Supporting Information

SI Table 1. Total detections of Willow Warbler (WW), Spotted Flycatcher (SF), and Common Chiffchaff (CC) by study region and monitoring method.

Region	Species	BBS Detections	eBird Detections	Audio Detections
Kristiansand	WW	95	34	425
Bergen	WW	65	1	2431
Trondheim	WW	88	5	158
Tromsø	WW	36	1	124
Stavanger	WW	48	2	29
Moss	WW	88	18	41
Lillehammer	WW	58	0	3
Kristiansand	SF	4	4	97
Bergen	SF	2	2	88
Trondheim	SF	3	0	4
Tromsø	SF	0	0	0

Stavanger	SF	0	0	8
Moss	SF	13	10	1
Lillehammer	SF	0	0	0
Kristiansand	CC	9	2	1
Bergen	CC	8	2	339
Trondheim	CC	51	9	151
Tromsø	CC	0	5	0
Stavanger	CC	2	2	0
Moss	CC	6	7	0
Lillehammer	CC	3	0	0

SI Table 2. Audio Species Distribution Model (aSDM) model hyperparameters, as well as test and train set mean absolute error (MAE) for Willow Warbler and Spotted Flycatcher. Predicted aSDM values range from 0.0 to 1.0. One Random Forest model was trained for each species and hyperparameters were chosen over 1000 iterations of randomized parameters to optimize the test set MAEs.

Species	Train MAE	Test MAE	Random Forest Parameters
Willow Warbler (<i>Phylloscopus trochilus</i>)	0.0761	0.226	{'n_estimators': 386, 'min_samples_split': 2, 'min_samples_leaf': 1, 'max_features': 'log2', 'max_depth': 80, 'bootstrap': True}
Spotted Flycatcher (<i>Muscicapa striata</i>)	0.0301	0.0704	{'n_estimators': 176, 'min_samples_split': 2, 'min_samples_leaf': 1, 'max_features': None, 'max_depth': 100, 'bootstrap': True}

Paper 4:

Building a Nature Soundscape Generator for the Post-Biodiversity Future: A pilot machine learning model for generating infinite pseudo-natural soundscapes

A. Bick

Proceedings of the Conference on AI and Musical Creativity. 2023;

<https://aimc2023.pubpub.org/pub/soundscapes>

Contribution Statement:

Aggregated global soundscape datasets. Designed, built, and trained PyTorch model to generate soundscapes. Wrote the manuscript.

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Building a Nature Soundscape Generator for the Post-Biodiversity Future

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Abstract

Exposure to nature has been linked to physiological and psychological wellness. As global biodiversity continues to decline, our opportunity to build a meaningful connection to nature follows. The loss of complexity in natural soundscapes is a bellwether for such biodiversity loss. Sounds of nature have been shown to calm our minds, ease our bodies, and connect us to our environments. Thus, we must preserve them for future generations. Here, I present a pilot generative model for the creation of pseudo-natural soundscapes to provide a pseudo-connection to nature for the post-biodiversity world. Trained on thousands of hours of nature soundscapes from across the world, the model demonstrates the ability to generate completely novel digital soundscapes as hybrids of currently existing natural ones. Further work in this area will ensure unlimited pseudo-nature sounds for the future despite biodiversity collapse.

Introduction

Biodiversity loss is occurring across the planet and across species. A 2019 Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services report found that the average abundance of native species has fallen by at least 20 percent since 1900. This is due in large part to loss of habitat from human development, including tropical and boreal forests and over 85 percent of wetlands [1]. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change reports have also identified that climate change processes drive biodiversity collapse, including increasing wildfires and shifts in seasonal timings [2].

Soundscapes reveal much about the natural, geological, and anthropological processes at play in a given area. For example, they convey information about vocalizing species such as birds, insects, and frogs which are crucial indicators of environmental health [3]. Biophony, the sound produced by organisms in a given environment, has decreased in parallel with biodiversity, reducing the complexity of soundscapes globally. A 2021 study by Morrison reconstructed historical soundscapes using North American and European bird survey to study these changes. From the 1990's until 2018, they predicted decreases in several indices correlated with biodiversity, as well as an increase in Acoustic Evenness which is correlated with a loss of biodiversity [4].

Nature and its biodiversity deserve protection for their own sake. However, our relation with nature is also critical in supporting human health, purpose, and community. Many studies have demonstrated the benefits of exposure to nature for improving health through reduction of stress [5], improvement of attention [5], and lowering violent crime rates [6]. Others have found positive correlations with nature exposure and personal reports of meaning in life [7] and sense of community identity [8]. Soundscapes are a critical way in which we connect to our surroundings, and humans, unsurprisingly, prefer natural soundscapes to anthropological ones such as those in cities [9].

If the ecological and climatic trends presented by the IPDES and IPCC continue, biodiversity and the complexity of natural soundscapes will continue to reduce. However, our innate need to connect to nature will

nevertheless remain. While virtual natural soundscapes, such as those created by Morrison, could be viewed as an "extension of nature" and not nature in themselves [10], it may come to be that we rely on these as a replacement for the real thing. Virtual natural soundscapes have shown some of the same stress reducing effects as real nature [10][11]. Medvedev, for example, found that the skin conductance (a measure of stress) of subjects listening to natural sounds recovered to baseline levels faster than subjects listening to busy city recordings[11].

The motivation of this study is to continue to provide natural soundscapes provide humanity despite biodiversity collapse, as well as to generate completely novel soundscapes. For this purpose, a convolutional variational autoencoder (CVAE) on approximately 1700 hours of natural soundscapes recorded across the world: Norway, France, Ukraine, Borneo, the United States, and China. The model encodes approximately four-second soundscapes as mel-spectrograms with alternating convolutional and max pooling layers, followed by a single linear layer before the model's latent space. The decoder mirrors the encoder, using alternating convolutional transposes and upsampling layers to return a [128,128] mel spectrogram.

By exploring the latent space of the CVAE, one can generate novel soundscapes that are combinations of the input data. For example, the model can slowly morph between two geographic regions and/or two time periods; several examples of this are illustrated and sonified in this pilot study. This ability to generate a wide array of new nature soundscapes will become increasingly useful if current trends continue, as future generations will have less complex and more homogenous soundscapes globally [4].

Related Work

A variety of machine learning techniques have been applied in previous works for generation of audio, including variational autoencoders [12], audio waveform diffusion [13], spectrogram diffusion [14], and generative adversarial networks [15]. Methods vary based on application, the amount of available data, and the length and complexity of the audio samples. For example, training on raw audio waveforms can create high-resolution outputs, but may struggle with long-term dependencies. In contrast, training on spectrogram images can create somewhat noisy outputs, but may more easily identify longer-term patterns [16].

Data

Sources

Bergen

Recordings from passive acoustic monitoring performed under the [Sound of Norway project](#), a project in which the author is involved. It includes dawn recordings from June 2023 with many bird vocalizations as well as a prevalence of rain. It consists of 12,000 5-second files after processing.

BirdVox-DCASE-20k

A dataset of 20,000 10-second samples recorded from autonomous recorders near Ithaca, New York in the fall of 2015. The data were filtered to those labeled as having bird detections by the dataset authors, about half of the files. A total of 11,684 5-second samples were utilized from this source. Downloaded from [Zenodo](#).

Borneo

A dataset of recordings in the rainforest of Borneo during afternoons in June 2019. Soundscapes are lush and busy and include birds calls and insect drones. Provided by Sarab Sethi and the SAFE project. Consists of 11,760 5-second files after processing.

Chernobyl

Recordings from passive acoustic monitoring inside the Chernobyl Exclusion Zone that includes bird, insect, and mammal vocalizations. This data set served as an evaluation set for the 2018 DCASE bird audio detection task. It consists of 10,558 5-second files after processing. Downloaded from [Zenodo](#).

China

Recordings by Ray Tsu (Xeno Canto ID: FROVFAFTMA) in the Tianlin Community of Shanghai, China. All recordings are from Spring months from 2020-2022. They include multiple species including the Chinese Blackbird, Pale Thrush, and the Yellow-browed Warbler. Consists of 6,224 5-second files after processing. Files downloaded from Xeno-Canto.

France

Recordings by Stanislas Wroza (Xeno Canto ID: SDPCHKOHRH) in the Grande-Rivière Château commune within the Jura department and Bourgogne-Franche-Comté region of France. All recordings are from evenings in March 2021 and capture the call of the Boreal Owl. Consists of 12,953 5-second files after processing. Files downloaded from Xeno-Canto.

Ithaca

Recordings from a stationary microphone outside the Cornell Lab of Ornithology in Ithaca, New York. Provided by Holger Klinck and Chris R. Pelkie. Two sub-classes are included, a summer class including recordings from dawn hours in July 2018 and a winter class including dawn recordings from January 2016. The summer class includes 16,865 5-second files after processing and the winter class includes 15,685 5-second files.

Preprocessing

All data sets were converted to WAV files with a sample rate of 16000 Hz and 16-bit depth. Frequencies below 300 Hz were removed to eliminate low-end noise and increase model clarity on mid and high frequencies and

the biophony present in the samples. Using Python, all files were then sliced into 5-second segments. Using the Librosa library, mel spectrograms were generated from each WAV file using a FFT window length of 2048 and a hop length of 512. Spectrograms were converted to decibel scale, then normalized from 0 to 1. The tail of the spectrogram was then cut to give a final square shape of [128,128] for simpler convolutional operations in the CVAE model.

Further preprocessing steps were applied to achieve a normal distribution of input data and ease model training, due to the normal distribution of data in CVAE latent space. First, the data was clamped to a max value of 0.5. Data was then split into a training set (80 percent), validation set (15 percent), and test set (5 percent). Then a min-max scaler with a range of (0,1) was fit to the training set, and applied to transform each of the three sets. The final training, validation, and test sets had 78107, 9763, and 9764 samples, respectively.

Model

The soundscape generator model is a convolutional variational autoencoder built in PyTorch Lightning (SI Fig. 1) with 9.4 million trainable parameters. It was built upon a basic framework of a [pytorch variational autoencoder](#) provided by Medium author and data scientist Reo Neo.

The encoder consists of 5 segments, each with a convolutional layer, a ReLU activation, and a max pool layer. Stacking convolutional layers in this fashion in theory allows for capturing of lower level features like borders and edges in shallow layers and capturing of intricacies and patterns in deeper layers. Additionally, as the input spectrogram images are quite large for network of this small size, the max pool layers are used both compress the spectrograms and highlight frequency-time regions with greater energy. A single linear layer of size [2048] connects the encoder to the latent space. The decoder is a reversed version of the encoder, with upsampling layers instead of max pool layers to increase image size.

The latent space consists of two linear layers of size 1024, representing the mean and log variance of the latent distribution. Variational autoencoders, in contrast to standard autoencoders, have a latent space consisting of a high-dimensional normal distribution, which these layers encode. This is intended to create a smoother latent space for sampling and generating new outputs lying between input classes.

The model was trained for 51 epochs using a learning rate of 0.00001, a batch size of 4, and the Adam optimizer. The loss function was the per-image sum of mean squared error (MSE) of validation set, which was found to improve temporal resolution compared to the mean MSE for each image.

Results and Discussion

The results indicate that a simple CVAE model can extract the general characteristics of soundscapes across the diverse data sets. Frequency-axis information, such as droning background sounds (Figs. 1d,1e) or long animal calls (Fig. 1f), were reproduced well. Temporally, the model blurred together staccato patterns (Fig. 1b) and fine details (Figs. 1a,1h) characteristic of animal vocalizations. As the model is trained on raw soundscape data

and not on animal call samples, the model may be converging on a solution to reproduce the droning background sounds, morphing any captured animal calls into soundscapes in the process. The resulting sounds have an uncanny quality.

Figure 1: Reconstructions of test set input spectrograms for each data set.

This effect can be heard in Soundscapes 1a and 1b, a sample from the China data set and its CVAE reconstruction, respectively. The essence of the original can be heard in the reconstruction, though detail of individual calls merge together. The model performs well on recreating an owl call from the French data set (Soundscapes 1c and 1d, Fig. 1f), possibly due to the longer notes already closely representing a droning sound.

The sound clips were below were generated from spectrogram images using the Griffin-Lim algorithm, which can create noisy artifacts, some of which were removed using the Adobe Audition Hiss Reduction Tool.

Soundscape 1a: China Spring Dawn test set sample (Fig. 1g)

Soundscape 1b: China Spring Dawn reconstructed sample (Fig. 1g)

Soundscape 1c: France March Evening test set sample (Fig. 1f)

Soundscape 1d: France March Evening sample reconstruction (Fig. 1f)

Novel soundscapes were then generated by performing linear interpolation between sets of two test set samples. Figure 2a and 2b illustrate how characteristics of two distinct soundscapes blend into each other, merging a calm winter soundscape in Upstate New York with a spring dawn chorus call from Shanghai, China, for example. The transition of these two soundscapes can be heard in Soundscape 2b, which plays through each of the five spectrograms shown in Figure 2b. Equalization and light reverb added in Ableton Live.

Figure 2: Latent space soundscape interpolations between two encoded test set samples for a) the France March Evening and Ithaca Summer Morning data sets, b) the Ithaca Winter Morning and China Spring Dawn data sets, and c) between two samples from the Borneo June Afternoon data set.

▶ 0:00 / 0:20 🔊 ⋮

Soundscape 2a: France to Ithaca interpolations, audio for five spectrograms from Fig. 2a

▶ 0:00 / 0:20 🔊 ⋮

Soundscape 2b: Ithaca to China interpolations, audio for five spectrograms from Fig. 2b

Using the dimensionality reduction algorithm [UMAP](#), the 1024-dimensional latent space embeddings for the test set were reduced to two dimensions for visualization. Figure 3 illustrates the clustering of the data sets in this high dimensional space.

Smooth soundscape interpolations between test set samples were found between within the same data set (Fig. 2c) and in data sets that have overlap in the UMAP plot (Fig. 2b, Fig. 3). However, noise is introduced interpolating between the France and Ithaca Summer Morning data sets, which appear not to overlap in the latent space (Fig. 3). In the future, incorporating Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence loss in addition to sum of MSE as a loss function could improve interpolations by forcing the model to adopt a more normally distributed latent space. However, in the current architecture, implementing KL loss caused further blurring of features in generated spectrograms.

Figure 3: UMAP 2-D clustering of 1024-D model latent space for all test set samples.

Conclusions

The pilot CVAE model presented here demonstrates the ability to reconstruct samples across a broad data set of soundscapes and shows that new soundscapes can be generated by interpolating between those derived from currently existing ecosystems. However, it struggles with capturing high-temporal resolution information and

blurs animal calls into their surroundings. Application of more complex deep learning models, higher audio sample rates, and tuning of the soundscape data set could lead to more convincing and hi-fidelity pseudo-natural soundscapes for future generations to enjoy.

Acknowledgments

Thanks to the owners of all data sets used to train this model for providing them directly or allowing for open non-commercial usage.

Supporting Information

```

=====
Layer (type:depth-idx)      Output Shape      Param #
=====
c_vae                       [128, 1024]      1
├─Sequential: 1-1          [128, 1024]      --
│   └─Conv2d: 2-1          [128, 32, 126, 126]  320
│     └─ReLU: 2-2         [128, 32, 126, 126]  --
│       └─MaxPool2d: 2-3  [128, 32, 63, 63]   --
│         └─Conv2d: 2-4   [128, 64, 61, 61]   18,496
│           └─ReLU: 2-5  [128, 64, 61, 61]   --
│             └─MaxPool2d: 2-6 [128, 64, 30, 30]   --
│               └─Conv2d: 2-7 [128, 128, 28, 28]  73,856
│                 └─ReLU: 2-8 [128, 128, 28, 28]  --
│                   └─MaxPool2d: 2-9 [128, 128, 14, 14]  --
│                     └─Conv2d: 2-10 [128, 256, 12, 12]  295,168
│                       └─ReLU: 2-11 [128, 256, 12, 12]  --
│                         └─MaxPool2d: 2-12 [128, 256, 6, 6]   --
│                           └─Conv2d: 2-13 [128, 512, 4, 4]   1,180,160
│                             └─ReLU: 2-14 [128, 512, 4, 4]   --
│                               └─MaxPool2d: 2-15 [128, 512, 2, 2]   --
│                                 └─Flatten: 2-16 [128, 2048]        --
│                                   └─Linear: 2-17 [128, 1024]        2,098,176
├─Linear: 1-2              [128, 1024]        1,049,600
├─Linear: 1-3              [128, 1024]        1,049,600
├─Sequential: 1-4        [128, 1, 128, 128]  --
│   └─Linear: 2-18        [128, 2048]        2,099,200
│     └─Unflatten: 2-19  [128, 512, 2, 2]   --
│       └─Upsample: 2-20 [128, 512, 4, 4]   --
│         └─ConvTranspose2d: 2-21 [128, 256, 6, 6]   1,179,904
│           └─Upsample: 2-22 [128, 256, 12, 12]  --
│             └─ReLU: 2-23 [128, 256, 12, 12]  --
│               └─ConvTranspose2d: 2-24 [128, 128, 14, 14]  295,040
│                 └─Upsample: 2-25 [128, 128, 28, 28]  --
│                   └─ReLU: 2-26 [128, 128, 28, 28]  --
│                     └─ConvTranspose2d: 2-27 [128, 64, 30, 30]   73,792
│                       └─Upsample: 2-28 [128, 64, 60, 60]   --
│                         └─ReLU: 2-29 [128, 64, 60, 60]   --
│                           └─ConvTranspose2d: 2-30 [128, 32, 62, 62]   18,464
│                             └─Upsample: 2-31 [128, 32, 126, 126]  --
│                               └─ReLU: 2-32 [128, 32, 126, 126]  --
│                                 └─ConvTranspose2d: 2-33 [128, 1, 128, 128]  289
│                                   └─Sigmoid: 2-34 [128, 1, 128, 128]  --
=====
Total params: 9,432,066
Trainable params: 9,432,066
Non-trainable params: 0
Total mult-adds (G): 56.57
=====
Input size (MB): 8.39
Forward/backward pass size (MB): 1155.07
Params size (MB): 37.73
Estimated Total Size (MB): 1201.19
=====

```

SI Figure 1: Convolutional variational autoencoder architecture

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Paper 5:

Simulated Environments and Environmental Consciousness: Extending Ecoacoustic Monitoring into Sound Art

A. Bick

Under Review

Preprint available at doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14254324

Contribution Statement:

Performed relevant research, literature review, and audio data mining with Python, created the sound art case study of the Sound of Norway project in Ableton, and wrote the manuscript.

Simulated Environments and Environmental Consciousness:

Extending Ecoacoustic Monitoring into Sound Art

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Abstract

This article explores how greater interplay between science, technology, and art can facilitate deeper connectedness with nature and large, distributed natural processes, such as global warming and avian migration. The author, an ecoacoustic data scientist and musician, lays a foundation by discussing how the sublime aesthetic characterizes our appreciation of nature, the myriad benefits of nature immersion, and the ability of art—particularly sound art—to facilitate a connection with natural hyperobjects. The author then applies these concepts in several sound art pieces derived from bird detections within the *Sound of Norway*, a national-scale passive acoustic monitoring network.

Technology, Ecology, and Connectedness to Nature

Recent technological advances in computing and sensing have enabled revolutionary new approaches for monitoring ecosystems. Passive acoustic monitoring (PAM), an ecological method growing in popularity and showcased in this paper, leverages autonomous (often solar-powered) acoustic recorders and machine learning algorithms to automate the detection of species vocalizations in-situ [1], enabling ecologists to compile high resolution data to study migration dynamics [2] and human impacts on biodiversity or animal behavior [3]. Such technology effectively expands ecologists' senses over vast distances and long time periods, supplementing in-person surveys. Outside of ecological research, technological advancement is clearly not a panacea

for socio-environmental harmony, as the increasing prevalence of digital technology and digital media environments has led to a loss in nature connectedness [4], defined by Zylstra et al (2014) as a “stable state of consciousness comprising symbiotic cognitive, affective, and experiential traits that reflect, through consistent attitudes and behaviors, a sustained awareness of the interrelatedness between one’s self and the rest of nature.” [5-6] With myriad studies underscoring the positive effects of nature connectedness on attention [7-9], stress [10], and even life satisfaction [11], these trends are concerning, to say the least. Technology seemingly provides us with a greater scientific understanding of nature while simultaneously dissociating us from it.

Reversing such widespread disassociation from nature should particularly concern conservationists. In their work *Connectedness as a Core Conservation Concern*, Zylstra et al present the argument that nature connectedness builds upon both scientific understanding of nature as well as actual experience and immersion within nature, eventually leading to environmentally responsible behavior [12-13]. Malcolm Budd makes a parallel point in *The Aesthetic Appreciation of Nature*: “aesthetic appreciation is deeper the more it is penetrated by and the product of [scientific] knowledge” [14], suggesting that scientific understanding of nature’s processes helps one appreciate nature as nature and not as an art object [15]. Through a scientific understanding of bird migration, for example, a person living in the northern hemisphere may form a greater appreciation and respect for birds that arrive in the spring, knowing the vast distances they have traveled. Thus, the bio-environmental sciences form a foundation for us to understand our relation to nature and appreciate its processes and vast spatiotemporal scales. However, as any climate scientist may tell you, scientific understanding alone cannot facilitate collective action on pro-environmental issues.

The massive spatiotemporal scale of natural processes presents an impediment to increasing collective nature connectedness and pro-environmental action. Timothy Morton frames environmental concepts such as ecosystems or global warming as “hyperobjects”, defined as objects “massively distributed in time and space relative to humans” [16], thereby making them only partially accessible to our senses and difficult to relate to emotionally or aesthetically. Indeed, the fact that we can only perceive a “small time slice” [17] of an ecosystem presents a problem for the appreciation of the aesthetic value of that ecosystem. Art plays a critical role in overcoming (or at least alleviating) this issue by immersing us within hyperobjects in creative ways. An oft-cited example of ecological art, the 2015 piece *Ice Watch* by Olafur Eliasson and Minik Rosing,

consisting of twelve large pieces of ice carved from the Greenland ice sheet, installed near the COP21 climate summit in Paris [18]. Passersby could interact freely with the piece as it gradually melted onto the pavement, a tactile and direct experience with the hyperobject of global warming [19]. One may compare this aesthetic experience to an analogous scientific one, such as using remotely sensed imagery from satellites to derive rates of ice sheet retreat over time in Greenland. Scientists may use technology to study nature at huge scales, but deriving nature connectedness solely from data and associated graphs seems challenging at best. It again becomes clear how science provides a critical knowledge base upon which art can facilitate the development of our “relationship to non-humans” [20].

In this paper, I first establish the importance of the sublime aesthetic for establishing connectedness with and appreciation of natural hyperobjects, then discuss how art may leverage technology to act as an extension of nature, expanding our senses and ability to experience these hyperobjects, providing examples of notable previous work. I then endeavor to enact these principles by leveraging soundscapes and bird detections derived from the national-scale PAM project, the *Sound of Norway*. By using these distributed acoustic sensors in tandem with a generative audio scheme, I mimic long-term temporal flows of soundscapes across the latitudinal extent of Norway in a compressed form, allowing listeners to experience the hyperobjects of large-scale forest soundscapes and avian migration in a previously impossible way. Through this effort, I contend that art can contribute to bridging the gap between scientific understanding and nature connectedness.

Perception of Nature and Art

In the 18th century, Kant effectively distinguished the aesthetic experiences of the *beautiful* and the *sublime*, useful frameworks for teasing apart aesthetic experiences of art and nature. The *beautiful*, generally confined to a bounded object such as a painting or sculpture, may elicit pleasure through a judgment of taste or quality. Conversely, *sublimity* indicates an indirect pleasure, or “negative pleasure” [21], produced from awe and respect for nature’s unboundedness or quantity. This sensation is characterized by the momentary suspension of the conscious mind and its subsequent expansion [22]. The chaos, magnitude, and inherent lack of objective in nature can thus both humble and inspire us. We may fixate externally on a beautiful object, but the sublime forces us inward. In short, “the sublime touches, the beautiful charms” [23].

In the 20th century, scientists, philosophers, and the public became increasingly aware of deleterious effects of industrialization and overconsumption on the natural world. The field of environmental aesthetics re-emerged alongside the conservation movement as a reaction to this [24]. In a seminal work by Ronald Hepburn in 1966, *Contemporary Aesthetics and the Neglect of Natural Beauty* [25], the author argues that contemporary aesthetics had focused too greatly on the art world, and suggests that modern approaches to nature appreciation incorporate “approaches that accommodate not only nature’s indeterminate and varying character, but also both our multi-sensory experience and our diverse understanding of it” [26]. Indeed, there exists a distinct difference between experiencing one’s environment aesthetically versus a painting or a film. We typically find art-objects distinctly separated from their surroundings via a frame, a stage, or a velvet rope. These boundaries lend a sense of distinctness and completeness, starkly in contrast with the ambiguity and vastness of the natural world. In a nature-experience, we are “*in nature and a part of nature*, we do not stand over against it as over against a painting on a wall” [27], this immersive aspect of nature arguably provides a space for self-experience and self-reflection, even facilitating feelings of “one-ness”.

The seeking in nature for art-object qualities, such as the *picturesque* (imagine a postcard of Yosemite or Mount Everest) and the finite, arguably lead to an unappreciation of the whole and thus an inability to experience the sublime or derive a sense of one-ness from nature experience. Thus, I argue that for an authentic extension of natural sublime to occur through art, the typical art-object boundaries must be blurred. This can be accomplished through playing with immersion, scale, and perspective in a variety of mediums, such as earth art (see *Wheatfields for Manhattan* by Agnes Denes [28]), architecture, or by leveraging digital mediums like virtual reality and sound art.

Extending Nature with Simulated Environments

One may argue that the most sublime perceptions of real nature are those which hint at its vastness. The view from a coastal cliff, for example, reveals the curvature of the earth, hinting at laws of gravity which form planets and galaxies. While one can undoubtedly experience the sublimity of the natural world through their own vision, hearing, smell, and touch, some aspects of the natural world are more difficult to aesthetically integrate than others. Ecosystems, for example, are somewhat fuzzy environmental hyperobjects that extend over large spatial distances, cycle over

variable time periods (diurnal, annual, etc.), and consist of many interweaving biological relationships. Our sensory limitations prevent us from fully aesthetically appreciating the totality of ecosystems' spatial and temporal scales, as we might for an artwork such as a painting, book, or a film [29]. Perhaps this inability to experience the totality of an ecosystem aesthetically impedes a full appreciation of natural beauty and thereby, the development of environmental consciousness. This applies equally to other environmental hyperobjects such as forests, migration, or global warming. Indeed, research indicates that aesthetic appreciation of nature strengthens nature connectedness [30], which has been identified as a key driver of pro-environmental behaviors [31].

Expanding the potential scope of our aesthetic experience may strengthen our connectedness with hyperobjects like ecosystems or our emotional integration of wicked problems like global warming. Art enables us to aesthetically experience such hyperobjects from new angles and in compressed forms, potentially developing an emotional connection to these broad and diffuse concepts. Technological approaches, such as virtual reality and sound art, have a critical role to play, due to their innate ability to stretch and compress space and time. However, these technologies would be erroneously viewed as replacements for nature, they instead offer an “extension of nature” [32] that supplements our existing natural experiences with novel viewpoints or shifts of scale. Still, studies have shown that these extensions of nature can bestow some of the beneficial psychological effects of actual nature immersion. Listening to natural soundscapes has been shown to facilitate stress recovery [33-34], and a review of virtual reality nature by Sharon Frost et al identified several studies associating it with decrease in negative feelings such as fear or anxiety [35], though more research is needed in this area.

Notable Previous Works

The virtual reality art piece *The Bone* [36], led conceptually by Chilean artist Michelle-Marie Letelier, utilizes visual cues, soundscapes, and spoken word to create an empathetic experience between the viewer and an animal subject. Sitting physically inside an old wooden fishing boat, the viewer puts on a VR headset and enters the 3D-rendered skull of a real wild salmon, while traditional Sámi Yoik song echoes in the background. A human voice echoes inside the skull, a stream of consciousness interpretation of the memories of this deceased wild salmon's life and freedom, soon contrasted with the memories of its brethren who spent their lives in a factory fish farm environment. Immersion in this “intermediate world — between deep sea and universe;

between present, future or past; between reality, dream or utopia” [37] pushes the viewer to experience for themselves this contrast and to consider how humans impact the lived experiences of animals from a novel perspective.

The piece *Longplayer* by Jem Finer [38] demonstrates how sound art excels at “attuning our senses to superhuman timescales” [39]. Beginning on December 31, 1999, six audio tracks started to play an identical musical piece in parallel at varying rates in a cycle not again aligning until the piece’s end in 2999 [40]. During a 2020 live performance of *Longplayer* in Amsterdam, Netherlands, one could experience the expansive timescales and slow evolution of the piece beside the typical hectic sounds of traffic in the city center outside [41]. *Longplayer* serves to remind the listener that hyperobjects unfold on long timescales alongside our daily lives and short-term concerns.

As with temporal scales, sound art facilitates our access to otherwise inaccessible spatial scales and perspectives. *Listening at the Seams* by Steven Hammer and Greg Sieber [42] uses sound objects to elucidate the effect of human development and pollution on the Schuylkill River in Pennsylvania. In one arrangement, the artists mix audio from microphones placed in discarded shotgun shells and a half-melted plastic bottle with recordings from a hydrophone in the river’s headwaters. The natural textures of water flow and bird song contrast with the artificial resonances of the plastic bottle and tubing, encompassing the environmental history of the river in a way inaccessible via a standard listening experience. Exploring this environment through this sound object blurs the line between human-created artifacts and nature, showing how while our actions disturb nature, they also become part of it.

The sound art piece *Explorations of Extraction and Decay* [43] by Merlin Coleman was performed at the spatial audio theatre Audium in San Francisco from 2023-2024 and exemplifies how spatialized sound art can effectively facilitate a connection between our emotions and broad socioenvironmental concepts. The piece takes place in two settings, a quarry and a landfill, embodying concepts of resource extraction and waste disposal, respectively. In each of these settings, Coleman interweaves field recordings of industrial excavators and dumping with snippets of conversations with concerned locals affected by and concerned by these operations including local government employees and ecologists, using the spatial aspect of the theatre’s speakers to create tension and release through the hectic or slow movement of sound sources and the illusions of them approaching or departing from the listener. Brief but impactful musical interjections

appear all around the listener, capturing and expounding upon the emotions that underlie their concerns of environmental destruction and pollution, emotions that are difficult to capture solely in words. In these ways, Coleman ties these processes of environmental extraction and waste dumping to human emotion, allowing the listener to aesthetically relate to these large-scale processes that we may hear of more commonly in drier scientific or journalistic fashions.

Case Study: The Sound of Norway

The *Sound of Norway* initiative, undertaken by ornithologists and data scientists through the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research, explores the capability of PAM to track biodiversity, rare species, and migratory dynamics over a national scale. During my PhD, I participated in planning and field work for this initiative, deploying several dozen autonomous recorders in Norwegian forests during the spring of 2022 (see Fig. 1a), through which over 37,000 hours of recordings were collected. These solar-powered stations (see Fig. 1b) used the Bugg platform [44] to collect audio at 44.1 KHz, which was saved with a compressed MP3 encoding in five-minute increments. The stations with reliable 4G cellular network access transmitted this audio to a cloud server, where we applied the BirdNET algorithm [45] to detect bird calls and identify species, splicing shorter audio files for each identification in the process. Our scientific goals included mapping changes in the species vocalization probability during their migratory arrival in the Spring, and understanding how automation could fill gaps in manual bird surveys (see our preprint for more information: [46]). However, the capturing of a vast number of ecological recordings over a large spatiotemporal scale lent itself naturally to studying these natural hyperobjects from an artistic angle as well.

Figure 1 – a) Map of *Sound of Norway* recording stations and total hours recorded per region. Norway shapefile sourced from Robert Hijmans [47]. b) Photo by author of a passive acoustic monitoring station with solar panel and Bugg recording device, set up as part of the *Sound of Norway* project.

A mixture of programmatic and random, generative techniques was applied in the curation of the three sound art pieces showcased here from environmental recordings. Using Python, I downloaded up to 30 random detected bird calls with a BirdNET confidence score over 0.50 (based on a scale from 0.0-1.0) for each combination of recording station, four-hour period of the day, and month (May, June, and July). To lessen background noise from the recordings, I captured a noise print from a silent example in Adobe Audition and applied its Noise Reduction Process tool with standard settings. In Ableton Live 11, a Sampler instrument was created for each period-region-month combination, and the corresponding samples were loaded into these Sampler instruments.

For the southernmost recording stations, those in forests near Kristiansand and Stavanger, the Sampler instruments were panned to the left of the recording. The northernmost ones, outside Tromsø and Finnmark, were panned far to the right (see Fig. 2). The center of the mix contains bird calls from Bergen, Lillehammer, and Trondheim. For each four-hour period, bird calls were randomly triggered for the Sampler instruments in each region for approximately 20 seconds, with

time in between triggered calls also randomized. After 20 seconds, bird calls captured during the next four-hour period were faded in, and the process continued as such. This procedure resulted in three sound art pieces accompanying this paper as supplementary material—*Norway Forests: May, June, July*—each of which portray a compressed version of the Norwegian forest biosphere hyperobject in the months of the avian migratory arrival and breeding season in Norway.

Figure 2 – Combined regional soundscapes for *Norway Forests: May* piece. The y-axis represents left-right panning of the regions in the stereo field, corresponding to the

relative latitudes of each region. The x-axis represents the relation between time of day where bird detections were sampled and the length of the piece.

Migrating birds begin arriving across Norway in the early spring. First, short-distance migrants such as Starlings (*Sturnus vulgaris*) and Thrushes, followed by long-distance migrants such as Willow Warbler (*Phylloscopus trochilus*) and Spotted Flycatcher (*Muscicapa striata*) in April and May, when migration activity peaks [48]. Likewise, vocalization frequency peaks upon migratory arrival in May, as individuals compete for territory and mates, then tends to decrease through June and July [49]. However, Norway stretches widely across latitudes, with northern and more mountainous regions generally receiving migrants later in the season when snow has melted. The *Norway Forests, May* piece showcases these broader trends. At our highest elevation recorders in the Lillehammer region, we only detected species during the dawn chorus, generally the period of diurnal vocal activity (see Fig. 2). Additionally, southern regions such as Kristiansand and Bergen show generally denser biophony—the collective acoustic signals generated by species—than northern regions such as Finnmark and Tromsø, which have sparser but sustained vocal activity, potentially due to the longer days in the north. In these northern areas, the sun never sets during June, with southern areas like Oslo and Kristiansand only receiving a few hours of twilight. This large-scale phenomenon becomes apparent through the panned audio in *Norway Forests* pieces, particularly in *June* and *July* where the “weight” of the pieces shifts slightly to the right ear towards the end of the piece in the evenings, representing the sustained vocal activity in the northern regions where the sun is not setting.

Future Work

Further explorations on this theme could involve extending this piece, currently optimized for headphones or stereo speakers, into a physical setting for public viewing. One may imagine a room or hallway lined with speakers, along which listeners could walk and experience the full soundscapes of Norway in a compressed spatiotemporal fashion. Such an idea was explored effectively by David Dunn et al in 2020 when presenting playback of parallel multi-channel recordings done of a lake ecosystem in Northern California [50]. Speakers were placed in a room at similar relative distances and locations to the original recorders at the lake, allowing the public

to experience both their own extended acoustic sense of this ecosystem as well as multiple points of audition (analogous to the visual concept of point of view), enabling them “to move through the space to perceive local nested details while still hearing the total soundscape that surrounds them.” [51] This style of playback allows listeners to easily traverse spatial scales of acoustically recorded environmental hyperobjects.

While the decision to use audio splices of bird detections was used in *Norway Forests* due to the relative lack of biophony density and recording quality in our Norwegian recordings, future pieces may consider using raw soundscape data like Dunn et al to more accurately portray spatial biophony patterns. A similar scheme to the spatial art pieces demonstrated here could also be applied to an aesthetic study of development gradients. For example, a series of microphones could record at increasing distances from development into an undeveloped forest and spatially panned for a listener, showcasing how anthropogenic forces reduce acoustic complexity and the biodiversity of vocalizing species [52].

Conclusion

Inspired by earlier sound art works, my motivation behind *Norway Forests: May, June, July* was to enable an otherwise impossible aesthetic experience of large-scale natural hyperobjects: annual bird migration, climate, and forest ecosystems, that has perhaps previously not been done at this scale. These works (and simulated environments in general) act as an extension of natural aesthetics [53] that facilitate our appreciation of nature’s sublimity. Ecologists—especially those collecting audio, images, or video of nature through their research—may consider collaborations with artists as a means of developing an emotional depth to scientific communication. The aesthetic, emotional dimension of nature connectedness that art can facilitate weaves well together with our scientific understanding of nature, together offering a more complete nature connectedness. In this way, art may reconnect science, which is often of a cerebral nature, back to the emotional level on which we often operate, both individually and collectively. However, while offering potential benefits, simulated nature cannot be regarded as a replacement for proper nature (see [54]), and artists and programmers creating such nature “extensions” should remain humble. As stated by EO Wilson in *Biophilia*: “Artifacts are incomparably poorer than the life they are designed to mimic. They are only a mirror to our thoughts” [55].

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